

STRATEGIC PLAN

2024-2028

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Centre for Ecological Research and Forestry Applications (CREAF) is a public research centre dedicated to terrestrial ecology, territorial analysis, and global change, pursuing excellence in the production and dissemination of knowledge, in addition to the innovation, development, and transfer of methodologies. The CREAM team (2023) includes 271 people working in research (78 permanent, of which 43 are PI, 36 postdoctoral researchers – including trainees –, 46 predoctoral researchers, and 84 research technicians), and 43 working in research management and administration (policy engagement, pre- and post-award offices, communication, research impact, academic talent and equity, fundraising, knowledge and technology transfer, infrastructures, modelling facilities, and TIC), including the general manager of the centre. The 50.05% of the whole CREAM team are women, who represent 41% of permanent researchers. (i.e., all researchers excluding postdocs and predocs), 27.9% of researcher PI's (i.e., leading projects) and 35.7% of staff joining CREAM's scientific boards and committees.

CREAF research is organised around four research areas and 8 excellence research groups (SGR) recognised by the Catalan Government. CREAM has experienced strong progress in research excellence during the period covered by the previous strategic plan (2014-2017, extended to 2023) and especially since the centre received its first Severo Ochoa award (end of 2019). Scientific production exhibits a steady increase across years up to 320 SCI articles in 2023. Furthermore, 91% of these articles have been published in journals in the first quartile (Q1) and 27.4% in the first decile (D1) in the last evaluation (2022). A recent benchmarking analysis showed that CREAM is the first among the centres analysed as for the number of publications and normalised

impact. CREAM also ranks first in terms of the percentage of international collaborations and in the percentage of these collaborations led by women. It also stands out in the number of publications per author, above the group average and the 75th percentile. These data confirm that CREAM is among the leading international centres in its field of research.

The recognition at Spanish level that came with receiving the Severo Ochoa award has gone hand in hand with growing international recognition, both of CREAM as a benchmark organisation in fields such as the impact of global warming, strategies to mitigate climate change and the conservation of biodiversity, and of its individual researchers. During the period 2017-2023, CREAM has intensified its participation in international networks, alliances, and expert working groups. CREAM has also shown remarkable success in H-Europe funding, with a three-fold increase in returns and a quadrupling of funded projects in recent years. Recently, CREAM has also strengthened its science-to-policy involvement through the participation in international and intergovernmental panels such as IPBES and IPCC and a new focus in science diplomacy.

CREAF has also deployed a highly skilled team of research managers during the last Severo Ochoa project that provides multiple support to CREAM direction and to research staff at any stage of their scientific career. Support of this team has helped to improve the collaborations among researchers, leading to an increase in co-authorship connections and network cohesion. CREAM's Ecosystem Modelling Facility (EMF), has enhanced CREAM's modelling capacity and collaborations among researchers. The team has also promoted the culture of impact in research and aligned CREAM's priorities with those of the EU,

by hiring one of the first Research Impact Officers in the Severo Ochoa programme. A Research Impact Strategy and its associated Impact Plans were developed to promote impact in all research proposals. The team also empowers researchers to improve their careers through specific Career Services.

The communication team has strengthened one of the best communication strategies in Spanish research centres, greatly increasing CREAM visibility. In the last years, CREAM has skyrocketed its communication to new heights, gaining 70% more social media followers, increasing visits to its news blog by an impressive 244%, and scoring over 300 media features despite intense competition. The centre has also engaged over 3,000 active volunteers in its citizen science projects and attracted 2,000 more newsletter subscribers, now totalling 6,500. CREAM's international communication has been developed by hiring a specific communication officer and developing an international communication plan to maintain communication with specialized thematic networks and develop an international newsletter. CREAM's communication team has also supported the development of several citizen science projects in various cities engaging over 3,000 active volunteers, and attracted 2,000 more newsletter subscribers, now totalling 6,500.

The CREAM team's research capabilities are strengthened by the availability of first-rate scientific infrastructures including 16 laboratories. CREAM's location on the campus of the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona also provides CREAM with access to the UAB Scientific and Technical Services. Highly specialised analyses requiring high-throughput DNA sequencing techniques and high-class bioinformatics expertise are carried out in collaboration with external platforms, mostly within CERCA.

CREAM is also strongly committed to creating a diverse and inclusive organisational culture and has

developed a strong EDI (Equity, Diversity & Inclusion) strategy. The organisation has hired an EDI officer that leads the EDI Committee and collaborate with the Management Team to monitor and regularly evaluate the action plan implementation. CREAM made significant strides in improving the gender balance of researchers during the 2018-2022 period (before and after the development of the first Severo Ochoa award), especially those in leadership positions, with the proportion of women rising from 17.1% to 32.7% for senior researchers (i.e., all excluding postdocs) and from 19.4% to 27.9% for PI's. We have also increased the percentage of women researchers serving on scientific boards and advisory committees from 20.8% in 2018 to 35.7% in 2022. Thanks to a revision of our recruitment policy, 60% of researchers recruited, both junior and senior, from 2019 to 2022 were women.

Thanks to long-term policy and strategic planning, CREAM now boasts a quite robust financial situation, with a steady increase in the incomes and of the diversification of its sources and a global balance between incomes and expenditures. The basic pillars of current CREAM's financial situation include (i) the securing of the Severo Ochoa award, in December 2019, and its renewal in March 2024, (ii) the Grand Agreement (2021-2024) with the Government of Catalonia, in renewal by 2025; (iii) a thriving flow of EU funding, and (iv) increased funding from transfer activities, with an average of €1.4 million per year. Thus, the favourable financial position of CREAM can be attributed to a combination of a budget secured by the Trustees and a heightened ability to obtain external funding from a variety of competitive sources, predominantly public but with an increasing proportion of private funding. This has led to the establishment of a 75-25 model, whereby external sources have contributed around 75% of the total budget over the last five years, indicating that income from external sources is roughly three times the monetary contribution of the Trustees.

Considering the results obtained to date, the societal, political and economic context, and the SWOT analysis, the following 4 strategic priorities have been established for the period 2024-2028 (developed in 16 strategic goals, 40 operational goals and 66 actions):

1. Conduct and foster excellent scientific research relevant in a changing global context that enhances our leadership positioning at the national and international level. Focus will put on maximising CREAM's contribution to solving the current and future major environmental challenges and on promoting a culture of excellence and internal collaboration, while seeking the international projection of our research and improving technologies and infrastructures for its the development.
2. To generate societal impact from CREAM's research, first introducing and fostering the impact perspective in our research strategy and practice, from planning to evaluation and including the development of consistent impact narratives. In this perspective, our science-to-policy work and our outreach activities shall require special attention. We will also analyse the market and social trends to find new opportunities for knowledge and technology transfer and we will develop a new KTT strategy.
3. To attract, retain and consolidate the talent that the centre needs to fulfil its mission. The priorities will be to fully develop the recruitment and talent management policies and systems, be able to attract the people the organisation will need to accomplish all their objectives, offer useful and comprehensive training programmes and career services, and foster the EDI (equitable, diverse & inclusive) culture within CREAM.
4. To ensure the centre's development and sustainability. We must, on one hand, reduce our CO2 emissions and implement procedures to be ecologically sustainable. On the other hand, we must explore our growing potential and take actions to guarantee the future increase of resources. Reviewing and improving our management model and creating the best work environment will be key assets for this purpose.

Image: Joan de la Malla

1. ABOUT CREAM

The Centre for Ecological Research and Forestry Applications (CREAF) is a public research centre dedicated to terrestrial ecology, territorial analysis, and global change, pursuing excellence in the production and dissemination of knowledge, in addition to the innovation, development, and transfer of methodologies.

It was founded in 1987 as a consortium, whose partners are the Government of Catalonia (Generalitat de Catalunya), the Autonomous University of Barcelona (UAB), the University of Barcelona (UB), the Institute of Catalan Studies (IEC) and the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC). CREAM is a member of the CERCA institution (Research Centres of Catalonia),

and it has an extensive network of collaboration with many national and international centres, which is reflected in joint projects, publications, and training activities.

CREAF strives to create new knowledge and innovative solutions on terrestrial ecology management and land-atmosphere-biosphere interactions that helps society to mitigate Global Change effects. Through scientific excellence, CREAM aims to be a world-class research institution, capable of expanding the frontiers of knowledge while tackling the biggest and most complex environmental challenges facing contemporary society.

1.1. STRATEGIC FRAMEWORK

CREAF's Strategic Plan 2024-2029 assumes and reinforces the mission it has been developing since 2013.

MISSION

CREAF's mission is to generate knowledge to understand nature through top-notch research and collaborate with society to find informed solutions to environmental challenges on a local, regional, and global scale.

VISION

CREAF works to become an international benchmark in ecology, territorial analysis and global change, focusing on the Mediterranean basin, and have a leading voice capable of influencing key decision-makers.

VALUES

Team and governing bodies of CREAM endorse the following values as a guide for their work and their performance as the centre representatives.

SCIENTIFIC EXCELLENCE

Researchers at CREAM are committed with excellent research, applying the highest standards and best practices in their work, and looking to maximise their contributions to society with impact-driven research.

COLLABORATION

Research and management of the environment and the territory are a collective responsibility and a collective challenge, which can only be tackled through collaboration between research centres, public administration, economic and social organisations, and citizens.

ETHICS AND EQUITY

CREAF is committed to the JEDI principles (Justice, Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion) and applies them in all dimensions of its activities, from research to dissemination and environmental and sustainability advocacy work.

FLEXIBILITY

The world is constantly and rapidly changing. Capacity to respond efficiently to this change as researchers and innovators is what will ensure CREAM's success as a leading scientific institution.

INDEPENDENCE

CREAF's ability to remain an independent entity is what gives strength to its voice, based solely on its expert knowledge and research results.

1.2. ORGANISATION AND GOVERNANCE

CREAF is a consortium of public institutions. The **Board of Trustees**, on which the member organisations of CREAM's founding consortium are represented, is the centre's highest governing body. It includes representatives from:

- Four ministries (departments) of the Government of Catalonia (Generalitat de Catalunya)
- Territory, Housing and Ecological Transition (DTER)
- Agriculture, Livestock, Fisheries and Food (DARP)
- Research and Universities (DREU)
- Home Affairs and Public Safety (DI)
- Institution of Research Centres of Catalonia (CERCA)
- Autonomous University of Barcelona (UAB)
- University of Barcelona (UB)
- Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)
- Institute of Catalan Studies (IEC)

The Board of Trustees has an **Executive Commission**, made up by three representatives of two Catalan Government departments (DTER, DARP and DREU), the representatives of UAB, UB and CSIC, and one representative of CERCA as observer institution. The Executive Commission carries out the agreements adopted by the Governing Council and is responsible for supervising research activities, approving the operational funds, and ensuring the annual objectives are met.

The current composition of the Board of Trustees and its Executive Commission can be found on the [CREAF website](#).

The Board of Trustees appoints the person in charge of directing CREAM, who has broad powers to carry out the management and administrative functions of the centre and its staff, and also acts as Secretary of Board of Trustees. Currently, CREAM Director is Dr Joan Pino.

The International Scientific Committee regularly evaluates the centre’s research work and results and, through its assessments and recommendations, ensures that CREAM’s research meets the highest international standards. It is made up of six internationally renowned researchers:

IVAN JANSSENS

Research professor at Research Group of Plant and Vegetation Ecology, Antwerpen University, Belgium

OPHÉLIE RONCE

Senior researcher at Institut des Sciences de l’Évolution de Montpellier, France

ROB JACKSON

Research professor at Nicholas School of the Environment, EUA. Duke’s Center on Global Change Director and Duke’s Stable Isotope Mass Spectrometry Laboratory director

JOHN GRACE

Emeritus professor of the University of Edinburgh, Scotland

PEP CANADELL

Chief research scientist at CSIRO Environment, Australia. Executive Director of the Global Carbon Project

BRIDGET EMMETT

Research professor at the UK Centre for Ecology and Hydrology, United Kingdom

As the organisation chart (figure 1) shows, the centre is organised into three sections: Research, Development & Training; Strategy & Promotion; and Administration & Internal Service.

Research, Development & Training includes all the centre’s scientific and technical staff. CREAM’s **scientific agenda** is organised around four general issues: biodiversity, global change, ecosystem functioning and Earth observation. Most of the permanent staff collaborate across these different research themes. The staff responsible for the main research facilities, including the state-of-the-art laboratories and the Ecosystem Modelling Facility (EMF), created during the Severo Ochoa award, are also part of the department.

Researchers are also responsible for PhD training, which is coordinated by a PhD coordinator together with CREAM's Academic Talent and EDI officer. The technical coordinator (hired in 2024) strengthens collaboration within CREAM staff and with this staff and external research institutions to create new opportunities for integrated research projects.

Strategy & Promotion supports research activity, and it is organised into five units: **Communication and Outreach** devises and implements the institutional communication strategy, creates communication and outreach plans for scientific projects, and supports outreach events. **Pre-award** provides support for international (mostly EU-based) and national project proposals, advising on R&I funding programmes, and promoting networking to establish project consortia. **Academic Talent & EDI (Equity, Diversity and Inclusion)** supports the professional development of researchers through high-quality training, mentoring programmes and a career development service, and contributes to a diverse and inclusive work environment. **Research Impact** supports planning, delivery, and assessment of societal impact of research into the centre's institutional and research projects, practices and strategies. **Policy engagement and institutional relations** unit promotes CREAM's networking with other research institutions and in the science-policy interface at international, national and local levels. **Strategic projects** section includes the scientific and general management of the Severo Ochoa Award.

Administration and Internal Services gathers six units led by the General Manager of CREAM. **Administration** manages the general accounting, treasury, and budget, while ensuring yearly audits for accountability. **Project Management** supports post-award phase of European and national projects and grants, handles legal and financial issues, and prepares and submits financial reports and audits. **People Management** oversees staff management at CREAM, including selection and recruitment procedures, on-boarding and off-boarding processes and labor payments. **Project post-award** coordinates the economic management of all projects and contracts. **Knowledge Transfer & Fundraising** fosters collaborations within the socio-economic system, with the KTT Officer and the Philanthropy Coordinator, helping researchers establish productive alliances with the private sector. **Technology Information (TI)** provides all units with the software equipment and TI services for developing their tasks.

To support the Director task there are in place two internal advisory boards, or commissions: a **Commission of R+D**, integrated by representatives of the CREAM's research groups (SGR) that provide advice and guidance on research strategy, and a **Commission of Strategy, Research Management and Administration**, made up of the heads of the main Strategy & Promotion and of Administration and Internal Services units.

CREAF'S ORGANISATION CHART

Figure 1: CREAM's organisation chart

1.3. TEAM AND CAPACITIES

The CREAM team (2023) comprise **271 people working in research** (78 permanent of which 43 PI, 36 post-doctoral researchers – including trainees –, 46 predoctoral researchers, and 84 research technicians) and **43 people working in research management and administration** (pre-award and post-award offices, communications, dissemination, research impact, academic talent and equity, fundraising, knowledge and technology transfer, infrastructures, modelling facilities, and TIC), including the general manager of the centre.

The research team includes two ICREA Research Professors (Maurizio Mencuccini, who works at CREAM since 2012, and Laia Andreu Hayles, who joined the centre in January 2022), and more than 60 external scientific collaborators participating in different groups.

The 50.05% of the whole CREAM team are women, who represent 41% of permanent researchers (i.e., all researchers excluding postdocs and predocs), 27.9% of researcher PI's (i.e., leading projects) and 35.7% of staff joining CREAM's scientific boards and committees.

The CREAM scientific team is organised into eight consolidated research groups (accredited and funded by the Catalan Government), detailed in the section dedicated to the [scientific agenda](#).

QUALITY IN RESEARCH MANAGEMENT

CREAM boasts a senior, multidisciplinary, and highly skilled team of research managers, whose quality and cutting-edge advice are endorsed by the prestigious European Association of Research Managers and Administrators (EARMA), of which CREAM has been a member since 2020.

Our team of officers is specialised in European R&I policies, research impact, academic talent, diversity, communication, intellectual property rights, open access, financial and legal aspects, and much more. They provide bespoke support for all CREAM research staff, at any stage of their scientific career, including technical training, finding funding opportunities, proposal writing, and international reputation promotion.

SCIENTIFIC INFRASTRUCTURES

The CREAM team's research capabilities are strengthened by the availability of first-rate scientific infrastructures. The centre's facilities include **16 laboratories** (see the list below) allowing the analysis and processing of samples with different experimental requirements. CREAM's location on the campus of the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona provides its researchers with access to the UAB Scientific and Technical Services, covering several other experimental methodologies. Highly specialised analyses requiring high-throughput DNA sequencing techniques and high-class bioinformatics expertise are carried out in collaboration with external platforms. Can Balasc station also houses a set of general and specialized labs managed jointly by CREAM and the Natural Park of Collserola.

CREAM holds three **reference collections**. The pollinator collection includes more than 30,000 specimens; another collection includes 7,500 Mediterranean tree cores; and the third collection consists of soil samples from forests and meadows throughout Catalonia characterised according to their physical, chemical and biological properties.

CREAF also has **three experimental research stations**, put in place to carry out long-term studies of different ecosystem types, and monitored for decades. The stations are placed in the Montseny (non-Mediterranean mountains), Prades (Mediterranean mountain), and the Garraf (Mediterranean lowland).

UAB LABORATORIES AND OTHER EXPERIMENTAL SPACES

LIST OF CREAM SCIENTIFIC FACILITIES

- Optics Laboratory
- Water and Air Pollution Laboratory
- Microscopy and Cultures Laboratory
- Acid Digestion Laboratory
- Molecular Ecology Laboratory
- Soil Laboratory
- GC/MS Laboratory and Biogenic Emissions
- PTR/MS Gases Laboratory
- Stable Isotopes Laboratory
- Chemistry Laboratory
- Pollinator Networks Laboratory
- Dendrochronology Laboratory
- Teaching practice laboratory
- Ecophysiology and Global Change Laboratory
- Conservation at -80°C and Incubation of Biological Samples
- Plant and Soil Drying Room
- Soil Fauna Extraction and Incubation Room

CAN BALASC LABORATORIES AND OTHER EXPERIMENTAL SPACES

- Can Balasc Ecology Laboratory
- Can Balasc Soil Biodiversity Laboratory
- Can Balasc Dendrochronology and Incubator Room
- Can Balasc Carpentry Module
- Can Balasc X-Ray Module
- Can Balasc Experimental Plot

COLLECTIONS

- Cores of mediterranean trees
- Forest and pasture soil collection
- Pollinators collection

OTHER

- EMF – Ecosystem modeling facility

2. SCIENTIFIC AGENDA

CREAF's research is organised in **four fundamental areas** and **six cross-cutting topics**, and the scientific strategy in place emphasizes the idea of **breaking down silos** and traditional disciplinary barriers to better address complex environmental challenges.

In this context, CREAM's scientific strategy focuses on promoting **interdisciplinary collaboration and integration**, aligning its research with the UN's [Sustainable Development Goals](#) (SDG), the [EU Green Deal](#), and initiatives such as the [Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services](#) (IPBES) and the [Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change](#) (IPCC).

This is achieved by fostering a culture of collaboration and participation, and by identifying specific goals and objectives relevant to both our research and our activities. The expertise of CREAM's scientific coor-

inator (Dr Alicia Pérez-Porro) has been a key asset in this process. She has promoted the development of our new strategic plan, in which we have used a participatory approach, with the support of an expert facilitator and advisor. This approach has given all researchers and staff the opportunity to participate in shaping our scientific strategy.

CREAF's eight research groups (SGRs) recognized by the Catalan Government are distributed across the four fundamental research areas. Because of the desire to continually break down silos, while CREAM researchers are designated to one of the four areas, they actively engage in all areas without restriction. This fosters seamless collaboration and the blending of expertise among our diverse research teams, enabling us to tackle complex challenges with a multi-disciplinary approach.

AREA 1. BIODIVERSITY

This area contributes to addressing the current biodiversity crisis by understanding the spatial patterns of its components, as well as its drivers and threats at various levels (genes, populations, communities, and ecosystems) at both ecological and evolutionary scales.

Groups included in this area are:

- **BIOCONS** (SGR-00889), led by Lluís Brotons (0000-0002-4826-4457), Joan Pino (0000-0003-0939-7502), Josep Maria Espelta (0000-0002-0242-4988), and Pilar Andrés (0000-0002-1290-1864).
- **ECOEVOCHANGE** (SGR-01334), led by Daniel Sol (0000-0001-6346-6949), Oriol Lapiedra (0000-0003-0383-0061) and Yolanda Melero (0000-0002-4337-1448).

AREA 2. ECOSYSTEM FUNCTIONING

This area aims to understand nature and its ecosystem services with a focus on ecological restoration, forest die-back, water governance, and the conservation of pollinators, among others. It includes the understanding and modelling of soil-biosphere-atmosphere interactions and the biogeographical distribution of functional attributes.

Groups included are:

- **PROTECSOLS** (SGR-01038), led by Xavier Domene (0000-0002-2951-1491) and Sara Marañón (0000-0001-9786-3977).

- **RESET** (SGR-00849), led by Jordi Martínez-Vilalta (0000-0002-2332-7298), Francisco Lloret (0000-0002-9836-4069), Eva Castells (UAB, 0000-0001-7423-2742), and Teresa Gimeno (0000-0002-1707-9291).
- **FOREST ECOLOGY AND FIRES** (SGR- 00843), led by Javier Retana (0000-0002-7505-9467), Jordi Bosch (0000-0002-8088-9457), Anselm Rodrigo (0000-0001-6341-0363) and Annelies Broekman (0000-0002-8961-0467).

AREA 3. GLOBAL CHANGE

This area addresses the understanding of the main components of human-driven global change (climate change, land use changes, pollution, wildfires, alteration of water and biogeochemical cycles, etc.), their drivers and their current and future effects on biodiversity and ecosystem functioning.

Groups included in this area are:

- **GECA** (SGR-01168), led by Jordi Catalan (0000-0002-2934-4013) and Marisol Felip (0000-0002-7631-8715).
- **GEU** (SGR-01333), led by Josep Peñuelas (0000-0002-7215-0150), Iolanda Filella (0000-0001-6262-5733), Jordi Sardans (0000-0003-2478-0219) and Sandra Nogué (0000-0003-0093-4252).

AREA 4. EARTH OBSERVATION AND GEOGRAPHICAL INFORMATION SYSTEMS

This area provides a powerful technical approach to the assessment of biodiversity patterns, ecosystem functioning and global change impact through the generation and publication of digital cartography and large datasets, GIS and RS tools and standards.

The group included is:

- **GRUMETS** (SGR-00554), led by Joan Masó (0000-0002-2983-4629), C Domingo (0000-0001-6822-8704) and Lluís Pesquer (0000-0002-7396-2468).

Image: Joan de la Malla

Our research strategy is rooted in a powerful mission: to understand and combat the unprecedented challenges posed by global change. By delving deep into the intricate relationships between global change (Area 2), ecosystem functioning (Area 3), and the precious biodiversity and ecosystem services that support all life on Earth (Area 1), we can gain valuable insights into the workings of our planet.

The next step is to vigilantly monitor and observe these processes (Area 4) while analysing the data using ecosystem modelling techniques and experiments to produce impactful research outputs in all areas. Our goal is to harness this knowledge to guide ecosystem management and environmental policies, developing robust adaptation and mitigation strategies to address global change head-on (figure 2).

Figure 2: CREAM's research areas integration

Research in the four areas also has six strategic crosscutting topics, focused on current environmental crises and the ways to address them. These topics are:

FORESTS

Aimed at studying the functioning and dynamics of forests under the current and future global change scenarios.

SUSTAINABILITY

Aimed at improving the sustainable management of ecosystems: landscapes and regions.

MEDITERRANEAN BASIN

Aimed at assessing the impact of global change on Mediterranean ecosystems.

CITIZEN SCIENCE

Leading the development of platforms to open science to the citizenship for addressing environmental challenges.

ECOSYSTEM SERVICES

Focused on the outcomes of ecosystem functioning on the provision of services that are essential for human wellbeing.

LARGE DATASETS

Developing new big data tools and methods for generating and exploiting environmental data.

3. SCIENTIFIC AND SOCIAL CONTEXT

This chapter places CREAM in the context of international research into ecology, environmental sustainability and climate change, comparing its scientific results in the period 2019-2022 (i.e. the development of the first Severo Ochoa award) with those of seven

other leading centres in these fields¹. The section also describes the global, European and national political context and reviews the centre's alignment with the main policy lines which aim to promote the green economy for a more sustainable planet.

3.1. TEAM AND CAPACITIES

An analysis of CREAM's scientific production was carried out in February 2023, comparing the results obtained by the centre in the period 2015-2017 and in the period 2019-2021 (table 1).

Table 1: CREAM's bibliometric results (2015-2017 versus 2019-2021)

Indicator		PRE (2015-2017)	POST (2019-2021)	%change
Total publications	*	591	790	33,7%
Documents citable	*	564	748	32,6%
% Docs citable	=	95,4	94,7	-0,7%
% Docs leadership		40,1	35	-12,7%
% Women authorship	*	17,4	20	14,9%
% Women led papers		16	14	-12,5%
Total citations		30.179	15.171	-49,7%
Citations per document		53,51	20,28	-62,1%
Normalized impact		2,26	1,84	-18,6%
Highly Cited Papers (top 10%)	*	163	196	20,2%
Relative Highly Cited Papers (top 10%)		2,89	2,62	-9,3%
Outstanding Papers (top 1%)		32	28	-12,5%
Relative Outstanding Papers (top 1%)		5,67	3,74	-34,0%
% International Collaboration	*	77	84,6	9,9%
% Int. Coll. Leadership	=	26,2	25,5	-2,7%
% Int. Coll. Women Leadership	*	8,9	10,3	15,7%
% Docs Open Access		70,4	65,8	-6,5%
% Public Private Partnership	=	11,7	11,1	-5,1%
% Public Private Partnership Leader		2,8	2	-28,6%

* Indicators showing growth / = Unchanged indicators

The main findings were that the production of total papers and citable articles raised by more than 30% and the percentage of publications authored by female researchers and the number of publications in the top 10% most cited in the world also increased between the two compared periods. Results also improved in terms of international collaborative publications and the percentage of these collaborations led by women researchers.

1. The data in this chapter come from the positioning analyses carried out prior to the presentation of the candidacies (in 2017 and 2023) for the two Severo Ochoa Awards obtained by the centre.

The study compared CREAM's results with those of seven international reference centres:

- WSL – [Swiss Federal Institute for Forest](#)
- UKCEH – [UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology](#)
- HUTTON – [The James Hutton Institute](#)
- NIBIO – [Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research](#)
- NINA – [Norwegian Institute for Nature Research](#)
- MTA-OK – [Centre for Ecological Research](#) of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences
- SYKE – [Finnish Environment Institute](#)

In terms of number of publications, CREAM is in fifth position among the centres analysed and, as table 2 shows², it stands out for having the highest value of the subset in terms of normalised impact (1,610).

In terms of excellence, the 225 documents in the top 10% most cited in the world place CREAM above the 75th percentile. Moreover, expressed in relative values, the centre's total output represents 2.2 times more highly cited documents (top 10%) than expected, the highest value within this subset of centres.

CREAM ranks first in the group in terms of the percentage of international collaborations (86%) and in the percentage of these collaborations led by female researchers (9.5%). It also stands out in the number of publications per author (8.6), above the group average and the 75th percentile. CREAM is also in first position in public-private collaborations.

These data confirm that, in terms of scientific production, CREAM is in an outstanding position among the leading international centres in its field of research.

Image: Joan de la Malla

2. Note that in the table, a comma is used as a decimal separator and a dot is used to indicate thousands.

Table 2: Bibliometric benchmarking: CREAM versus seven international centres (2019-2021)

Indicator	CREAF	WSL	CEH	J. Hutton	NIBIO	NINA	MTA-OK	SYKE	Average	p75
Total publications	1.072	2.546	1.806	1.532	1.166	1.069	976	927	1.387	1.601
Documents citable	1.015	2.443	1.719	1.415	1.122	1.016	944	889	1320	1491
% Docs citable	94,7	96,0	95,2	92,4	96,2	95,0	96,7	95,9	95	96
% Docs leadership	32,2	39,6	29,8	34,3	37,5	27,9	40,7	32,7	34	38
% Women authorship	19,3	18,9	27,1	30,0	32,7	21,8	27,5	55,2	29	31
% Women led papers	** 12,3	7,5	7,9	10,0	4,9	5,8	8,7	16,1	9	11
Total citations	15.830	36.149	28.123	18.712	11.316	13.574	9.888	11.451	18.130	21.065
Citations per document	** 15,6	14,8	16,4	13,2	10,1	13,4	10,5	12,9	13	15
Normalized impact	** 1,610	1,520	1,570	1,340	1,160	1,460	1,150	1,470	1,410	1,533
Highly Cited Papers (top 10%)	** 225	453	318	209	130	156	117	158	221	248
Relative Highly Cited Papers (top 10%)	** 2,220	1,850	1,850	1,480	1,160	1,540	1,240	1,780	1,640	1,850
Outstanding Papers (top 1%)	34,0	64,0	62,0	37,0	26,0	27,0	19,0	34,0	37,9	43,3
Relative Outstanding Papers (top 1%)	** 3,350	2,620	3,610	2,610	2,320	2,660	2,010	3,820	2,875	3,415
% International Collaboration	** 85,8	82,7	73,1	72,1	73,8	71,4	64,6	62,3	73,2	76,0
% Int. Coll. Leadership	** 24,3	26,8	16,3	18,7	20,8	14,6	19,4	13,2	19,3	21,7
% Int. Coll. Women Leadership	** 9,5	5,2	4,1	5,4	2,3	3,3	3,6	6,2	5,0	5,6
% Docs Open Access	64,0	83,1	84,2	71,5	79,1	86,1	83,6	81,1	79,1	83,8
% Public Private Partnership	** 11,6	4,9	7,5	3,6	2,7	4,7	4,7	2,8	5,3	5,6
% Public Private Partnership Leader	** 1,9	0,5	0,5	0,3	0,5	0,4	0,2	0,2	0,6	0,5
% Researchers with foreign education	16,3	20,0	32,6	37,2	20,3	15,9	9,5	7,5	19,9	23,4
% Researchers from foreign institutes	** 31,4	22,0	58,7	50,0	16,1	16,7	12,9	8,1	27,0	36,1
Total Authors (Affiliated authors)	124	369	454	371		151	89	242	257	370
Publications / author	** 8,6	6,9	4,0	4,1		7,1	11,0	3,8	6,5	7,9
Documents / author	** 8,2	6,6	3,8	3,8		6,7	10,6	3,7	6,2	7,5

**Values that lie above the percentile 75 within the subset of centres analysed

3.2. ALIGNMENT WITH POLICY AGENDAS

The world is facing multiple global socio-environmental changes, with significant regional and local impacts. They will particularly affect the Mediterranean basin, according to the latest reports of the [Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change](#) (IPCC), the [Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services](#) (IPBES) and the network of [Mediterranean Experts on Climate and environmental Change](#) (MedECC).

As pointed out in the above-mentioned reports, many components of these changes (e.g., climate change, land use change, urbanisation, biological invasions, and others) will strongly alter the composition, structure and functioning of ecosystems, challenging biodiversity conservation and the provision of ecosystem services.

The European Union is especially concerned about the far-reaching effects of these impacts and proposes a transformation of its economic model, the broad outlines of which have been defined in the [European Green Deal](#), launched in 2019. It underlines the need for a holistic and cross-sectoral approach in which all relevant policy areas contribute to the ultimate climate-related goal: EU climate neutrality by 2050. The deal includes a package of initiatives covering the climate, the environment, energy, transport, industry, agriculture and sustainable finance –all of which are strongly interlinked.

The Catalan Government is particularly aware of this problem and has launched various initiatives aimed at reducing the impact of climate change and adapting to its consequences.

The Catalan Government has endorsed the [Manhattan Principles](#), which recognise the need for an international and interdisciplinary approach to combat threats to life on Earth. The principles propose a holistic approach to preventing epidemics and epizootics and maintaining the integrity of ecosystems for the benefit of humans, their domestic animals and the functional biodiversity that sustains us all. As of 2020 and as a consequence of the COVID-19 crisis, these principles have taken on special relevance and justify a commitment to the ecology of health through the interdisciplinary work of ecology, veterinary medicine and epidemiology, among others, in coordination with the health administration.

On the other hand, the Catalan Government is firmly committed to the [UN 2030 Sustainable Development Goals](#). On 25 September 2019, the Catalan Government approved the National Plan for the implementation of the 2030 Agenda in Catalonia. It thus fulfils the mandate of the Government Plan for the 11th legislature, approved in April 2016, where the Government committed to take up the call of the United Nations General Assembly to develop ambitious national responses to implement the 2030 Agenda.

On 17 July 2018, the Government of Catalonia also approved the [Natural Heritage and Biodiversity Strategy of Catalonia](#), the strategic planning document that defines the roadmap for nature conservation policies in Catalonia until 2030. The Strategy is an essential document for implementing in Catalonia the provisions of the 1992 United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity, the 2011-2020 Plan that implements it and the European Union's 2020 Biodiversity Strategy.

Previously, the Catalan Parliament had passed Law 16/2017, of 1 August, on climate change, which represented a turning point in the response to this challenge from the institutions and society in Catalonia. In May 2019, the Catalan Government agreed to declare a climate emergency to achieve the objectives set out in the aforementioned law in terms of mitigation and adaptation to climate change.

The COVID-19 pandemic had a major social and economic impact that has affected the way we perceive the climate emergency and people's relationship with their environment. A major overhaul of production systems is underway, and the need to move towards a new knowledge-based economy that is socially and environmentally sustainable is becoming increasingly clear. There is **a growing need to generate new knowledge** to promote a circular economy that fosters a **more rational use of resources** and, above all, **reduces the negative impacts on ecosystems** (pollution, loss of biodiversity, desertification, etc.).

In Catalonia, the National Pact for the Knowledge Society (PN@SC), approved in May 2020, and the new Catalan Science Law, approved in December 2022, endorse the commitment of political forces and the main economic and social actors to this new economy based on research and sustainable innovation.

Within this framework, CREAM has an important role to play as a centre of reference in the study of biodiversity –and the threats it faces–, the functioning of ecosystems, and global change.

Image: Galdric Mossoll

4. OUTPUTS 2017-2022

4.1. RESEARCH

CREAF has experienced significant qualitative progress in research and research management in the period covered by the previous strategic plan (2014-2017, extended to 2023) and specially since the centre received the Severo Ochoa award (end of 2019).

In addition to the improvement in scientific production (see [section 4.1.1](#)), CREAM's research has benefited from the creation of new groups and the recruitment of several senior and postdoctoral researchers, a better gender balance in the scientific team and an increasing number of collaborations and interactions.

NEW RESEARCH GROUPS AND FOCUS

As a result of the development of the Severo Ochoa project, CREAM has made significant scientific advancements in understanding the environmental impacts of human activities, such as habitat fragmentation, biodiversity loss, and nature-based solutions. We thus promoted two Government of Catalonia-recognised Research Groups (SGR), one focused on studying the metapopulation ecology and evolutionary adaptation of organisms in human-altered ecosystems (ECOEVOCCHANGE, SGR-01334), and another focused on conserving biodiversity and ecosystem services in these ecosystems and landscapes (BIOCONS, SGR-00889). Also, the Earth Observation team at CREAM (GRUMETS, SGR-00554) has begun utilizing large sets of data collected from remote sensing and citizen science to evaluate and map ecosystem services in human-altered regions.

Moreover, the strategic programme U-Landscape (*Integrating urban ecosystems into regional ecology to improve human well-being*), designed for the Severo Ochoa award, was also an opportunity for expanding the research focus of CREAM to these human-altered ecosystems, landscapes and regions. Three senior researchers (Sandra Nogu, Oriol Lapiedra and Teresa Gimeno) and 14 predoctoral researchers were hired and assigned to this programme. Furthermore, several postdocs (including Yolanda Melero, F. Sayol, L. Cardador, K. Otsu, and L. Fuzessy) hired through the SO award and other calls, such as Beatriu de Pinos and MSCA, have also been working in this new research focus. Other CREAM staff also is actively engaged in 10 EU projects focusing on biodiversity, ecosystem services and nature-based solutions in both urban and peri-urban regions. Still, CREAM researchers have developed a range of services and tools to address urban challenges, such as ecosystem and biodiversity degradation caused by urbanisation, the urban heat island effect, air pollution, and invasive species, especially since 2018.

ENHANCED GENDER BALANCE AMONG RESEARCHERS

During the 2018-2022 period (before and after the development of the first Severo Ochoa award), we made significant strides in improving the gender balance of researchers, especially those in leadership positions, with the proportion of women rising from 17.1% to 41% for permanent researchers (i.e., all excluding postdocs) and from 19.4% to 27.9% for PI's. We have also increased the percentage of women researchers serving on scientific boards and advisory committees from 20.8% in 2018 to 35.7% in 2022.

To address any potential bias in recruitment, we critically reviewed our recruitment policy to ensure that women and men receive equal opportunities to develop and advance their scientific careers. As a result, 60% of researchers recruited, both junior and senior, from 2019 to 2022 were women. We have also implemented positive measures in all three researcher recruitment calls made under the Severo Ochoa award scheme to accelerate gender-balanced participation and representation, as for example setting a defined proportion of positions to be filled exclusively by women (1/3 for postdoc calls and 2/3 for senior calls).

EMPOWERING SCIENTIFIC INTERACTIONS

Collaborations and interactions among researchers have been deepened at CREAM in the last five years, leading to an increase in co-authorship connections and network cohesion, as shown by an external bibliometric report comparing 2015-2017 and 2019-2021 data: 5% increase in the number of connections, and reduction in the number of satellite groups, indicative of an increase in network cohesion. The average relationships per author increased by 52%, while the average density of the network increased by 29%. These changes indicate an increase in the overall number of connections, average connections per author, and global density of the network.

During the period covered by the previous Plan, we created the Vermont Internal Workshops, an initiative to tackle strategic research challenges, where researchers present their findings and engage in thought-provoking discussions. Another successful initiative has been our *Leading Synthesis Actions Programme*, which brings together CREAM scientists and international researchers from over 12 countries for immersive, week-long workshops.

CREAF's Ecosystem Modelling Facility (EMF), established thanks to the Severo Ochoa award, serves as a strong foundation for enhancing CREAM's modelling capacity and strengthening connections with the international modelling community. The EMF has prioritized defining and executing key activities, providing training and support to all CREAM staff in modelling, programming, and statistics, developing modelling tools to simulate vegetation function and dynamics at regional scales³, and reinforcing relationships with other groups at CREAM and beyond through participation in international research projects.

RECOGNITIONS TO CREAM RESEARCHERS

It should also be noted that four CREAM researchers (**Josep Peñuelas, Jordi Sardans, Jordi Martínez-Vilalta and Maurizio Mencuccini**) have been included in the Clarivate Analytics list of *World most cited researchers*. Dr Peñuelas, together with Dr Marc Estiarte, were included in 2021 on the list of the 1,000 **most influential scientists** worldwide in the climate field.

Some members of CREAM team have been distinguished with different **recognitions** since 2017: **Joan Masó** (GIS [geospatial interoperability] and RS [remote sensing] team leader) received in 2018 the Gardels Award for his outstanding contribution to advancing Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) vision into the world's GIS. Professor **Jaume Terradas**, founder and CREAM former director was honoured by the Catalan Government with the *Creu de Sant Jordi* in 2019; **Josep Peñuelas** become Fellow of the influential American Geophysical

<https://emf-creaf.github.io/medfate/>

Union in 2020, and he was awarded by the Spanish National Research Award in the area of science in 2023. **Iolanda Filella** was included among the top 200 women scientists in Spain. **Sandra Nogué** and **Marcos Fernández-Martínez** have been recently awarded two ERC grants: a Consolidator Grant (2021) and a Starting Grant (2022), respectively.

4.1.1. SCIENTIFIC PRODUCTION

The Severo Ochoa accreditation has been the catalyst that has propelled CREAM to reach new levels of scientific excellence. Scientific production exhibits a steady increase across years up to 320 SCI articles in 2023 (figure 3). Furthermore, 91% of these articles have been published in journals in the first quartile (Q1) and 27.4% in the first decile (D1) in the last evaluation (2022; figure 4).

Figure 3: Growth of CREAM SCI publications (2014-2023)

Figure 4: Percentage of CREAM SCI publications in Q1 and D1 in 2022

Additionally, a recent bibliometric analysis shows that the number of documents in the top 10% most cited worldwide has increased by a notable 20% from the 2015-2017 triennium to that of 2019-2021. There has also been a 15% increase in the number of publications led by female researchers and a 10% increase in international collaborations. CREAM's young researchers show remarkable independence and professional growth, signing 2 to 3 publications on average without supervisors and leading over 50% of them. A citation analysis showed that our research has influence beyond our core activities, reaching 103 different research fields. These new fields range from physics or materials science to humanities, such as art and philosophy, and other fields with potential impact on society like political science, commerce, or medicine.

4.1.2. SCIENTIFIC PRODUCTION

CREAF has shown remarkable success in H-Europe, with a three-fold increase in returns and a quadrupling of funded projects in recent years. Three ERC grants stand out: IMBALANCE-P SyG project (2013; J. Peñuelas), which quantified the responses of ecosystems in a world increasingly rich in N and C but limited in P; the TIME-LINES CoG project (2022; S. Nogué), which is assessing biodiversity change in islands; and the STOIKOS StG project (2023; M. Fernandez), which explores element-based functional ecology.

Other EU projects coordinated by CREAM have been: AD4GD (HEurope, 2022; J. Masó), aimed to co-create and shape the European Green Deal Data Space as an open hub for FAIR data and standards-based services that support the key priorities of biodiversity, climate change, and pollution; CONNECTINGEO (H2020, 2015; J. Masó), aimed to provide a broader knowledge base and accessible to support the needs of Social Benefit Areas (SBA) of the Group on Earth Observation (GEO) and its users addressing a range of issues to emerging Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) proposed by the UN; WATERINNEU (H2020, 2015; LI. Pesquer), aimed to create a virtual marketplace to enhance the exploitation of EU funded ICT models, tools, protocols and policy briefs related to water; MIDMACC (Life, 2019; J. Retana), exploring adaptation through the implementation and testing of different landscape management measures to meet climate change related challenges in marginal mid-mountain areas of Spain while improving their socioeconomic development; POLYFARMING (Life, M. Gracia, 2016; J. Retana), which created regenerative agriculture guidelines; and GREEN-LINK (Life, 2017; J.M. Alcañiz), which assessed how to restore desertified areas with an innovative tree growing method.

CREAF has also participated in many other EU projects. Regarding the development and implementation of the so-called Nature-Based solutions (NBS), PHUSICOS (H2020 2018; P. Andrés) was aimed to demonstrate that nature-based and nature-inspired solutions for reducing the impact of extreme weather events in rural mountain landscapes are technically viable, socially acceptable, cost-effective and implementable at the regional scale. NIEBLAS (LIFE 2019, V. Carabassa) is aimed at developing innovative methods of reforestation (based on reintroducing endemic native species), and of water capture using fog water collectors (FWC) in Macaronesian (Canary Islands) and Atlantic (Portugal) landscapes. CLEARING HOUSE (H2020, 2019; C. Basnou) aims to provide evidence and tools that promote the potential of urban forests as nature-based solutions (UF-NBS) for rehabilitating, reconnecting and restoring urban ecosystems. CONEXUS (H2020, 2020; C. Basnou) develops and expands the concept of NBS towards Nature Based Thinking with full integration into policy and practice across different sectors (public, private, research, third sector and civil society). UFOR-

EST (Erasmus+, 2021; C. Basnou) aims at promoting Europe’s innovation capacity among universities, cities and businesses to deliver a new approach to urban forests as providers of NBS. CARDIMED (HEurope 2024; P. Andrés) introduces a framework of NBS to build climate resilience in the Mediterranean biogeographical region, unifying individual efforts of regions and communities across different countries and continents.

As for biodiversity and ecosystem management for increasing resilience and adaptation to global change, SPONFOREST (Biodiversa, 2016; J.M. Espelta) examined the potential of spontaneous forest expansion as a cost-effective and politically feasible tool for reinforcing perennial green infrastructures of self-sustaining forests in fragmented landscapes. RESONATE (HEurope, 2021; J.M. Espelta) investigates how past and current site factors and management affect forest system resilience in different forest types and management systems across Europe; the project highlights and balances trade-offs in decision making and delivers user-oriented recommendations and decision support with specific tools. [BIOAGORA](#) (HEurope, 2022; L. Brotons) aims at developing a Biodiversity Science Facility to connect research results on biodiversity to the needs of decision-making in a targeted dialogue between scientists, other knowledge holders and policy actors. [WILDE](#) (HEurope, 2023; J.M. Espelta) introduces ‘climate-smart rewilding’ as an innovative restoration approach to create climate benefits while addressing other socio-environmental needs.

Table 3: New projects across years

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
All	17	34	34	29	54	49	51
EU	4	7	10	11	7	5	16
EU leaded	0	0	3	0	0	0	1

4.2. SOCIETAL IMPACT OF RESEARCH AND KNOWLEDGE AND TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER

CREAF is deeply committed to **promoting a culture of impact in research** and aligning priorities with those of the European Union. In 2021, CREAM hired one of the first Research Impact Officers in the Severo Ochoa programme. The Research Impact Officer developed a Research Impact Strategy and associated Impact Plans, promoting impact literacy among staff, and ensuring impact is adequately considered at the beginning of all research proposals (figure 5).

The tasks developed also include the first-ever *Analysis of CREAM’s Research Impact*. This assessment will enable us to gather, analyse, and showcase the impact achieved by our previous research, providing valuable insights for learning and assessment purposes. The Research Impact Officer co-coordinates the Task Force ‘Narrative and Impact’ within SOMMa KTi Working Group, highlighting the commitment to impact-driven research. Furthermore, the creation of CREAM’s Citizen Science (CS) Working Group has boosted interactions and synergies among staff working in CS entailing, among others, the training of over 60 schools on CS and nature.

Figure 5: CREAM's impact strategy

A classical element within the research impact strategy of CREAM has been its influence in local and regional policy making, which has been recently reinforced through specific agreements with regional and local administrations. The Grand Agreement with the Catalan Government, signed in 2021, has permitted a strong development of knowledge and technology transfer to regional policy making, while improving the economic stability of the centre. Agreements with the Barcelona City Council (2022) and the Barcelona Metropolitan Area administration (2023) have settled the basis for the development of KTT to local policies. This support has also allowed us to take strides in expanding our reach through participation in cross-border collaborations and innovative projects, including the prestigious Interreg Sudoe, Interreg POCTEFA, H2020 and Horizon Europe programmes. Since 2018, CREAM is also participating in green infrastructure planning and the creation of guidelines for the Barcelona Metropolitan Area through the Metropolitan Lab of Ecology and Territory of Barcelona (LET-BCN).

The hiring of the KTT Officer and a Philanthropy Coordinator has enhanced CREAM's ability to apply research for economic development and societal benefits. This has permitted an increasing involvement in CREAM's KTT activities of private bodies and foundations, both national (e.g., the Caixa Foundation) and international (e.g., Earthwatch Institute, OGC, the European Spatial Agency), mainly interested in products and services for land planning. Finally, several tenders have been won to produce state of the art reports on strategic subjects (carbon farming, climate change, etc.) for governments and international organisations.

4.3. COMMUNICATION AND OUTREACH

CREAF has strengthened one of the best communication strategies in Spanish research centres, greatly **increasing CREAM visibility**. In four years, CREAM has skyrocketed its communication to new heights, gaining 70% more social media followers, increasing visits to its news blog by an impressive 244%, and scoring over 300 media features despite intense competition.

The centre has also engaged over **3,000 active volunteers in its citizen science** projects and attracted 2,000 more newsletter subscribers, now totalling 6,500. CREAM's **international communication strategy** has undergone a major transformation hiring an international communication officer and developing an international communication plan to attract international journalists, maintaining regular communication with specialized thematic networks, creating a map of audiences, interacting on social media, and developing an international newsletter.

Nowadays, CREAM collaborates with the Global Strategic Communications Network, the European Climate Foundation or the Climate Centre of UK, all international networks of communications professionals in the fields of climate and nature comms, as well as with AMWAJ alliance, an initiative that brings together communication and media stakeholders from the Mediterranean area.

NEW OUTREACH ACTIONS

We have also launched several citizen science projects in various cities. These include the [Citizen Observatory of Urban Butterflies](#) (uBMS) and the [Metropolitan Butterfly Monitoring Scheme](#) (mBMS) focused on butterfly observation in urban regions. It also includes the and the [Alerta Forestal](#) project, devoted to forest monitoring, as well as the [RitmeNatura](#) project, founded by Pla Clima of the Barcelona City Council to promote the reconnection of the city's population with nature through phenological monitoring. These projects are helping us to engage citizens in the scientific process and to gather valuable data that can inform our research and urban planning initiatives.

EVENTS & NETWORKING

In 2022, CREAM co-organized with CIDOB and Barcelona City Council the workshop [Boosting Euro-Mediterranean Urban Climate Action in the run-up to COP 27](#), to discuss next steps for climate action in the region's cities. Also, in 2020, Barcelona won the title of [European Forest City 2022](#), thanks to a joint initiative led by AMB, CREAM, IAAC, and CTFC.

4.4. ACADEMIC TALENT AND EDI

Obtaining the Severo Ochoa award in 2020 has proven to be a game-changer in our talent attraction strategy. We received over 100 applications and recruited six exceptional postdoctoral researchers through two open calls in September and November 2021. Our selection process and unwavering commitment to career development have borne fruit, as four of them have gone on to permanent positions.

We launched a call (2021) for three senior researchers who are now leading cutting-edge research, one of whom won an ERC-CoG. We have also significantly strengthened our customized internal programmes that improve CREAM's participation and success rate in the ERC and MSCA-PF programmes. Specifically, an efficient research management service has facilitated the recruitment of top-tier international talent. Over the past four years, this service has enabled us to secure one ERC-StG, one ERC-CoG, and six MSCA-PF fellowships and four Junior Leadership La Caixa.

NEW EDI STRATEGY

CREAF is strongly committed to creating a diverse and inclusive organisational culture and has developed a strong EDI (Equity, Diversity & Inclusion) strategy. The organisation has hired an EDI officer that leads the EDI Committee and collaborates with the Management Team to monitor and regularly evaluate the action plan implementation. The renewed plan includes an intersectional approach that recognizes how different social and cultural conditions interact simultaneously on inequalities and discrimination. To further promote these goals, CREAM's EDI officer is part of CERCA Gender Commission and the executive commission of SOMMa Gender WG.

CAREER SERVICES

CREAF empowers researchers to improve their careers through Career Services. The services, established for the first time with the Severo Ochoa project, include bi-weekly scientific seminars, quarterly training programmes for developing transferable research skills, curated resources on the intranet, career development sessions for early-career academics, and individual tailored sessions. These sessions cover topics such as academic and non-academic career opportunities, CV preparation, and interview techniques. Additionally, CREAM has implemented its first postdoctoral mentoring programme to guide postdoctoral researchers' career development, capitalize on the expertise of PIs and to grow the talent pool within the centre.

4.5. INTERNATIONALISATION

The recognition at Spanish level that came with receiving the Severo Ochoa award has gone hand in hand with growing international recognition, both of CREAM as a benchmark organisation in fields such as the impact of global warming, strategies to mitigate climate change and the conservation of biodiversity, and of its individual researchers.

CREAF researchers have also been required as experts to write world reference reports. Thus, in 2018, CREAM coordinated a NEMOR⁴ report for the European Commission about environmental challenges in the management of mountain regions. Dr Pilar Andrés was selected in 2019 for writing the FAO report on the state of soil biodiversity and, a year later, she was part of the writing team of the Eklipse European report to restore biodiversity. Also in 2020, CREAM and CTFC (Forestry Technology Centre of Catalonia) were commissioned by Catalan Government to write the report State of Nature in Catalonia 2020, and CREAM researchers participated in the production of the impactful MedECC⁵ report on the risks of climate and environmental change in the Mediterranean.

4. Network for European Mountain Research

5. Network of Mediterranean Expert son Climate and environmental Change

We expanded our international network by adding collaborators from 21 different countries between 2015-2023. Despite pandemic-related obstacles, we continued the Mobility Programme, opening international research opportunities for renowned foreign researchers to stay at CREAM and early-career researchers from our centre at institutions abroad. Over two years, we welcomed seven foreign researchers and sent seven young researchers across the globe.

During the period 2017-2023, CREAM has intensified its participation in international networks, alliances, and expert working groups, summarised below:

- EPI-AGRI Focus Groups (such as the [New Forest Practices and Tools for Adaptation and Mitigation of Climate Change Group](#))
- [Euromontana](#) (European Association of Mountain Areas)
- [Network of European Mountain Research](#) (NEMOR)
- [ALTER-Net Europe](#)
- [Group on Earth Observations](#) (GEO)
- [European Forest Institute](#) (EFI)
- [Forest-based sector European Technology Platform](#) (FTP)
- Network of [Mediterranean Expert son Climate and environmental Change](#) (MedECC)
- [Society for Ecological Restoration](#) (SER)
- [European Open Science Cloud](#) (EOSC)

At this stage, CREAM has also strengthened its involvement in **science diplomacy**. In 2021, the centre joined the [Global Coalition 'United for Biodiversity'](#) promoted by the European Commission to boost coordinated actions with tangible impact aimed at bending the curve of biodiversity loss. CREAM also was observer organisation at the 8th IPBES⁷ Plenary Session (June 2021) and has been organising and participating in different events to promote the political debate around environmental challenges, such as Increasing Awareness of Science Diplomacy in the Mediterranean, co-organised with the Union for the Mediterranean (UfM) in October 2021; Science Diplomacy: speak 'science' and enter, held in November 2021; Science Diplomacy and Climate Change: The Mediterranean as a global testbed, organised by COP27 and UfM; and Science Diplomacy in the Mediterranean: Building Trust Through Science and Knowledge, organised by the European Institute of the Mediterranean (IEMed) and Blanquerna-URL, in January 2023.

4.6. FINANCIAL STATUS

Thanks to long-term policy and strategic planning, CREAM now boasts a more robust and stable financial situation, with a steady increase in the incomes and of the diversification of its sources (table 4), and a global balance between incomes and expenditures (with more than 80% of these last corresponding to staff costs). This has enabled CREAM to weather the economic storms of the last decade in Spain. The basic pillars of current CREAM's financial situation include:

6. In the 2017-2022 period, CREAM has participated every year in the GEO Week Global Initiative and is GEO Associate since 2018.

7. Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services

- **Securing of the Severo Ochoa award**, in December 2019, **and its renewal** in March 2024. Beyond the evident recognition of the CREAM research at national and international levels, the award provided €4 M and 14 predoctoral contracts for the 2019-2023 period and will provide €4.5 M and 10 contracts more for the 2024-2027 period.
- **Grand Agreement (2021-2024) with the Government of Catalonia** (Generalitat de Catalunya), which is **due for renewal** by 2025. It provided a growth in ordinary income (i.e. that devoted to CREAM functioning and to ordered tasks by the Catalan Government). This strategic partnership has made it possible to allocate more funds to the centres' core activities, consolidating CREAM's position as a leading organisation for researchers, policy makers, and managers committed to global change adaptation and mitigation.
- **Increased funding from transfer activities**, with an average of €1.4 million per year over the past 6 years, driven by the Grand Agreement with the Generalitat (which accounts for about two thirds) and also supported by contracts with other regional and local institutions (such as the Barcelona and Girona Province Councils, the Barcelona Metropolitan Area and the Barcelona City Council, and the Water and Waste Agencies of Catalonia) and private companies (e.g. CaixaBank and the European Space Agency).
- **Thriving flow of EU funding**. In the period from 2018 to 2023, we have secured EU funding of an average of €2.5 million per year, which accounts for a staggering 32% of our total budget in the period (table 3). This success is demonstrated by 42 ongoing projects in 2023, founded by the programmes Horizon Europe, MSCA, Interreg, LIFE, and Biodiversa, and 30 proposals submitted in 2023 (table 4). Our innovation focus is validated by increased EU-public procurement through more frequent tendering.

Table 4: CREAM income (M€) from the main sources

	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Ordinary (Generalitat)	1.31	1.34	1.71	1.88	2.55	2.65
EU calls	1.77	2.16	1.91	1.72	3.52	3.85
National (Spanish calls)	1.13	1.42	2.98	3.06	2.61	3.95
Private & Others	1.06	0.56	0.34	0.42	1.42	1.60
TOTAL	5.27	5.48	6.94	7.08	10.10	12.05

Table 5: Number of proposals submitted to EU calls (Horizon Europe, MSCA, Interreg, LIFE, and Biodiversa) and their corresponding budget asked for CREAM (M€)

	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
No. of proposals	34	39	40	36	31	30
M€	11.6	13.7	9.7	17.9	6.0	7.6

- **Remarkable surge of Spanish R&D funding**, increasing from €1.13 M in 2018 to €3.95 M€ in 2023. The securing of the Severo Ochoa Award but also the staggering 80% success rate in applications to the Spanish Government research programmes (manly Retos) is a legacy of the previous Strategic Plan effectiveness. Particularly important is the increase in the number of young researchers who have been awarded one of these projects.
- **Increase in private funding** from €1.06 M in 2018 to €1.60 M€ in 2023. These funds were secured through competitive calls, such as national and international tenders, and other incipient non-competitive sources. The centre has also used the Severo Ochoa Award to strengthen its fundraising strategy, resulting in the first philanthropic donations in CREAM's history in 2022, amounting nearly €20,000. Most of the donations came from corporate donors, but individual donors also made contributions through an online platform.

To sum up, the centre's strong financial position can be attributed to a combination of a budget secured by the Trustees and a heightened ability to obtain external funding from a variety of competitive sources, predominantly public but with an increasing proportion of private funding. This has led to the establishment of a 75-25 Model, whereby external sources have contributed around 75% of the total budget over the last five years, indicating that income from external sources is roughly three times the monetary contribution of the Trustees.

Image: Galdric Mossoll

5. RECENT HISTORY AND MILESTONES

In 2018, CREAM celebrated its **30th anniversary**, and the high level and scientific impact of its research in ecology and the environment carried out since its creation was endorsed in 2019 with the **Severo Ochoa accreditation** as a centre of excellence. These are probably the most important institutional

milestones of CREAM's last 5 years, together with the **renewal of the centre's management** –which took place on 1 April 2019, when Dr Joan Pino replaced Dr Javier Retana, who had held the post since 2005, as CREAM's director– and the signature of a new **Grand Agreement with the Catalan Government** (2021).

5.1. PREVIOUS PLAN

CREAM's previous Strategic Plan initially covered the period 2017-2021, and was extended until 2023, on the understanding that the development of the U-Landscape project for Severo Ochoa accreditation has led to an ambitious strategic focus of CREAM's research.

Chapter 3 summarises the main advances made in research, knowledge transfer, talent attraction and development, societal impact of research, and funding in the period 2017-2022, highlighting the contribution of the Severo Ochoa Award to their achievement.

To complete the analysis, we also include table 6, with the main indicators of the 2017-2021 Plan showing the degree of achievement at the end of the period.

Table 6: Indicators of CREAM's Strategic Plan 2017-2022

NOTE: We include the indicator name, the expected value in the 2017-2022 period, the achievement assessment, and its justification.

ASSESSMENT (SCORE) NOT ACHIEVED

INDICATOR	EXPECTED VALUE (MEAN)	SCORE	SCORE JUSTIFICATION
Map of the research lines of the centre (Y/N)	Y		In 2018, a first document was performed to discuss the research of the Centre and explore future ways; in 2021, another document was produced based on a participatory process within the hiring process of Severo Ochoa senior scientists.
Number of recruited senior researchers	4		CREAM has hired or ascribed a larger number (n>8) of researchers in the recent years, considering the contracts done within the SO award and the secondment of ICREA, UAB and UB researchers with a focus on women PI
Number of postdocs per year	11		The number of postdoctoral researchers hired at CREAM ranged between 25 and 35 in the last 6 years

INDICATOR	EXPECTED VALUE (MEAN)	SCORE	SCORE JUSTIFICATION
Number of technical and support staff	50		The number of technical and support staff was over 60 in the last five years
Number of technical and support staff with permanent contracts	27		In 2021, the number of technical and support staff was 20, thus clearly below the SP threshold. However, the approval of the new Spanish Laboral law has changed the situation as the majority of CREAM technical and administrative staff can be considered as permanent. Moreover, there is a plan for stabilizing 15 people in 3 years, thus overcoming the threshold of the SP
Average h-index of researchers at the centre	22		The 50 permanent researchers, either hired or seconded, have a mean H-index of 28.6 in 2022. This is the outcome of a general increase of senior scientists but also for the hiring of new junior and senior ones.
Number of total SCI articles per year, Q1 and Q2	135		Publications in SCI journals ranged from 170 to 300 in the last 6 years. Publications in Q1 journals ranged from 80 to 90%. The rest are mostly published in Q2 journals.
Number of granted international projects led by CREAM	5		A larger number is achieved, especially taking into account Life, Interreg and some Horizon Europe.
Percentage of researchers sharing articles or projects	10%		No clear calculation rules were indicated in the previous Strategic Plan. We have considered the proportion of researchers sharing activity with more than 3 researchers of other SGR teams. Approx. 22% of researchers achieved this level of interaction.
Grant of the certification HR Excellence in Research	Y		The HRS4R label was awarded in 2015 and renewed in 2021 and 2024
Ranking of international positioning of the centre	Y		Two rankings were performed: one in 2017 with the Severo Ochoa application and another in 2020 for the CERCA assessment.
Map of international partners	N		Pending, in course with the Scientific Coordinator
Number of researcher exchanges	20		The average number of researcher exchanges in the last 5 years has been 19.5, 22.5 if we exclude the year of the COVID lockdown (2020)
Number of permanent contacts with international centres	70		30 through Alter-Net 40 through NEMOR 114 at GEO Several through MedECC and SapfluxNet and different research projects
Number of projects with international centres	22		In the last 6 years, the number of alive projects with international partners was clearly over 30

INDICATOR	EXPECTED VALUE (MEAN)	SCORE	SCORE JUSTIFICATION
Number of activities carried out in Can Balasc	6		>40 activities have been done in Can Balasc, especially in 2021 and 2022, after the arrangement of facilities and the COVID-19 lockdown.
Diagnosis of the transfer potential of the centre (Y/N)	N		Pending, in course with the recent joining of the Tech Transfer
Established protocol (Y/N)	N		An internal protocol on knowledge transfer to potential users was drawn up within the HRS4R actions, but it should be revised.
Number of projects granted, and agreements awarded per year	20		>37 projects and contracts start, on average, each year of the last five.
Increase in the number of users (individuals and institutions)	4%		CREAF has strongly increased the number of data servers (MiraMon servers; Catalan Data cube; Catalan Forest Lab, etc.) thus increasing the number of users much more than planned.
Number of transfer activities per year	19		The level has been achieved according to the data of annual reports, but some actions were not done.
Number of available databases	>5		CREAF has strongly increased the number of data servers (MiraMon servers; Catalan Data cube; Catalan Forest Lab, etc.). The level was achieved but data are dispersed: more actions are needed.
Number of entries in forums on environment discussion per year	24		53 outreach activities; about 110 conferences per year the last 5 years
Number of participations and formal recommendations per year	4		The Director J. Pino, the Scientific Coordinator (A. Pérez-Porro), the Research Impact officer (A. Sánchez) and some researchers (L. Brotons, S. Herrando. B. Claramunt, J.M. Espelta) are regularly involved in advisory and consultancy fora at regional, national, and international levels.
Report of the strategy of alliances of CREAM (Y/N)	Y		Pending, in course with the recent creation of the Area of institutional relations
Operating Income + Canon – Structural Expenses > 0	>0		According to financial data in Annual reports, this has been achieved in 75% of years; after the signature of a Grand Agreement with the Catalan Government in 2021 this has been reinforced.
Rate of income inequality	0.3		Discarded
Number of competitive proposals from the centre	41		About 50 proposals per year in the last 5 years (data known for EU projects, estimated for national projects).
€ obtained through projects / € obtained by contributions of trustees	2.55		> €2.80 M/year

INDICATOR	EXPECTED VALUE (MEAN)	SCORE	SCORE JUSTIFICATION
Budget Investments = Real Investments	±7,5%		Partially achieved (thanks to SO award)
Degree of use and satisfaction of infrastructures and services	Y		Scheduled for late 2024
Review procedure (Y/N)	Y		Pending
Satisfaction survey	Y		Survey HRS4R
Job pool at CREAM (Y/N)	Y		Done, as part of the CREAMs HRS4R & OTM-R Policy (www.cream.cat/en/join-us)
Evaluation system (Introduced/not introduced)	Y		Introduced and applied in 2016 and 2022
(i) Creation of the Scientific Board,	Y		Done, meeting minutes available
(ii) Creation of a space of discussion for researchers,	Y		Partially done (Vermuts, Cafes científics, etc.)
(iii) Development of the scientific code of ethics	Y		In development. Ethic Code of CERCA adopted
Number of training hours	132		Done (average 121 h/year in the last 5 years)
Number of training actions carried out per year	1.75		Average of 4/5 per year (last 5 years)
Number of students enrolled per year	47		Average of 60 students per year in 3 different masters
Number of PhD students enrolled per year	10		The mean of the last 5 years is 11.6 (data only for the PhD programme in Terrestrial Ecology)
Number of specialized courses per year	4		Implemented in the HRS4R and the Career Development (Watering Talents)
Number of seminars per year	11		CREAM Talks implemented (more than 15 seminars per year)
Number of blog visits per year	45,000		>45,000 from 2015
Number of webpage visits per year	55,000		>55,000 from 2017
Number of newsletters opened per year	10,000		>50,000 from 2021
Number of general impacts in the media	142		>200 from 2016
Number of impacts in national media (excluding Catalan media)	163		It is estimated in about 175 per year

INDICATOR	EXPECTED VALUE (MEAN)	SCORE	SCORE JUSTIFICATION
Number of impacts in international communication channels	8		The international communication service was not launched until 2020 within the Severo Ochoa award, but has got an average of >25 impacts per year in the last 3 years
Total number of participants in workshops	1,250		>2,000 in the period
Satisfaction survey for workers			Survey HRS4R
External survey on brand perception (Y/N)			Pending

5.2. SAB AND CERCA EVALUATIONS

In 2021, both the CREAM's Scientific Advisory Board and CERCA ([Research Centres of Catalonia Institution](#)) issued evaluation reports on the centre. Both reports follow on from the assessments carried out in 2016. The main findings of the latest SAB and CERCA reviews are detailed below.

CREAF'S SCIENTIFIC ADVISORY BOARD ASSESSMENT OF 2021

CREAF's Scientific Advisory Board was created in 2012 and drew up a first Scientific Review of the centre, which include a set of recommendations. In 2016, the SAB made a positive evaluation of the CREAM achievements –even though it highlighted the large gender imbalance that still persisted– and considered the centre well prepared to submit a candidacy for a Severo Ochoa accreditation, which CREAM obtained in 2019.

Five years later, in 2021, the SAB was made up by the same members as in 2016 plus two more that partially addressed the gender unbalance of this board: Bridget Emmett (Centre for Ecology & Hydrology, UK) and Ophélie Ronce (CNRS Université de Montpellier, France).

That year, the new board did another mandatory assessment of CREAM. It acknowledged a massive progress made since the last evaluation, and that the main recommendations made in 2016 were mostly addressed, often going well beyond what was proposed.

The SAB considered that CREAM is now in a strong position to address the 21st century's main environmental problems, including climate change and biodiversity loss, especially regarding southern Europe. It also highlighted that progress has been made across-the-board and in many different areas (science strategy, communications, gender, infrastructure) all directed towards better support for the centre mission and ensuring CREAM's leading role.

The progress is even more remarkable because all this has been achieved in a challenging period due to economic difficulties and the COVID-19 pandemic. The SAB saw this as the basis for CREAM's continued

progress and growth, striving to include all staff. Also, that further growth is inevitable and that more staff and laboratory facilities will have to be foreseen.

RESEARCH STRATEGY

The SAB celebrated the focus on ERC grants and considered that the success rate of CREAM can increase by (i) ensuring the creativity and novelty of the proposals, (ii) developing a strong system to promote applications including mock interviews to train applicants, (iii) encouraging early career scientists to apply, while maintaining the current level of support for more advanced researchers, (iv) encouraging re-applications by those receiving an 'A' in the evaluation process, (v) inviting successful ERC people (especially early career) to give talks on their experience, and (vi) increase contacts with people on ERC Panels to learn the system better, among other actions.

Finally, it also suggested considering some additional areas that are in growth, at least in the EU missions: soil health and the UNSDG goal of land degradation neutrality, and microbiome and links to ecosystem function.

ORGANISATION

The SAB highlighted the increase in staff and the quality of service provided and recommended improving the balance between management and science staff. It also suggested doing annual evaluations and reward processes for all staff and exploring opportunities to increase job security and to promote career development. It also recommended developing a strategy for increasing stabilisation of young researchers, promoting access to international networking and to other careers beyond academia.

According to the SAB, CREAM should also encourage young researchers to apply for funding sources to travel abroad and encourage PIs to include postdoctoral researchers as official CO-PIs and to promote their work as supervisors of PhD students.

The SAB also recommended making gender, equity and inclusion training mandatory, promoting online courses and striving to integrate it into CREAM's culture. It also suggested taking action on work-life balance, leading to a more equitable distribution of care responsibilities, and taking into account the role of governance and internal communication in fostering this culture change. In terms of funding, the SAB suggested continuing to focus on increasing private funding, without losing sight of the ethical issues and conflicts of interest surrounding this diversification.

The SAB also considered the promotion of internal networking as a priority and proposed that initiatives such as informal social and cross-group science events, science days and other regular social events should be encouraged. It also recommended further improving internal communication and means for bottom-up suggestions.

INTERNATIONALISATION

Regarding the international strategy of CREAM, the SAB recommended promoting visiting scientists from abroad and focusing on one-year fellowships with funding to support accommodation for foreign research-

ers. It also suggested exploring opportunities of collaboration with Latin America and continuing to invest into Mediterranean research networks.

CERCA EVALUATION OF 2021

In 2016, the CERCA Evaluation Commission (EC) performed its second assessment of CREAM with the presence of its Scientific Advisory Board. This is a compulsory assessment according to the National Pact for Research and Innovation, which states that all research centres in Catalonia must undergo a regular assessment of their activities and strategies. In that evaluation, the EC considered that CREAM achieved a good level of implementation of the recommendations stated in the first report (2012), despite some issues should be improved in the next years, mainly to increase internationalisation of the staff, to pursue a gender-balanced recruitment, and to give a major support to PhD mobility. As a result, CREAM was awarded with a qualification of B+.

In 2021, the CERCA EC performed its third assessment of CREAM. As in 2016, the EC was coordinated by Lluís Rovira (CERCA) and David Fernández (General Directorate for Research – Government of Catalonia). It included a set of external experts: Marion Bousquet (Station d'Écologie Théorique et Expérimentale SETE-CNRS, France), Anne Magurran (University of St Andrews, UK) and Nick J Wells (UKCEH Enterprise Limited, UK). It also included two representatives of the CREAM's SAB: Bridget Emmett (Centre for Ecology & Hydrology, UK) and John Grace (University of Edinburgh, UK). The EC agreed to award the maximum qualification in CERCA evaluations (A) to CREAM and reported its view of the centre and a list of recommendations:

Regarding **Scientific production and productivity**, the EC highlighted CREAM's scientific progress, with many CREAM researchers publishing in top journal publications and some of them being recognised as highly cited researchers. It also highlighted that CREAM obtained the Severo Ochoa award and that it has started to integrate research, outreach, and impact. However, the EC noted that CREAM has many small research groups and recommended to hold an internal discussion about their structure. The EC also recognised the great but unsuccessful effort made by CREAM to obtain ERC grants, and encourages to continue following this effort, striving to help researchers to work on the creativity, singularity and novelty of the proposals, and training candidates.

The EC also recommends definition of a clear agenda of talent attraction, offering interesting and especially attractive working conditions, since it is hard for CREAM to compete in salary with other international research centres. The EC also highlighted that CREAM has made clear progress in recent years in attracting more women to PI positions, and that it should continue in this direction, assisting female researchers to advance their careers and reach positions of high scientific responsibility.

Finally, the EC warned CREAM that it should devise a clear strategy for the renewal of the Severo Ochoa award. A special strategy should be defined for giving support to intermediate scientific staff that could become the next generation of top PIs in CREAM. It is also important to take care of the scientific career structure in CREAM, and to increase support for technical staff to better integrating them in the research projects.

Regarding **knowledge and technology transfer**, the EC encouraged CREAM to develop an integrated knowledge exchange strategy directly related to the CREAM impact action plan. This goes beyond the classical vision of technology transfer (patent licensing, spin-off creation, etc.), incorporating also the objective of having an impact on national, regional and international public policies. Importantly, an integrated knowledge sharing strategy must also be aligned with broader organisational plans, such as business development, internationalisation, communication and fundraising strategies, public engagement and approaches to measuring impact. Finally, the EC acknowledged the great work done on the communication strategy and recommended linking it to the other strategic objectives.

As for **management**, the EC considered that CREAM should increase support for researchers, especially about the process of drawing up proposals for EU competitive calls for projects. Additional funding to hire technical staff should always be included in project applications. The EC pointed out that the great need for additional space is a strategic challenge for CREAM, which should be addressed with the Board of Trustees.

The EC also recommends the promotion of social meetings with all staff in CREAM, thus contributing in a “natural” or informal way to the scientific outputs of CREAM. The EC also considers that CREAM should try to focus on the issues related to public engagement to reach the appropriate partnership and impact for the projects. Finally, the EC recognised the big efforts made by CREAM in recruitment actions in this last period, aligned with the HRS4R action plan.

Image: Joan de la Malla

6. CHALLENGES AND STRATEGIC PRIORITIES

6.1. SWOT ANALYSIS

A SWOT analysis of the centre was conducted by its Management Team to detect the internal strengths and weaknesses for the pillars considered in this Strategic Plan (see section XXX), as well as the current and future opportunities and threats of the CREAM's environment. This analysis stems from the discussions of this team combined with the recommendations of SAB and CERCA EC evaluations. The internal strengths and weaknesses and the external opportunities and threats are as follows:

STRENGTHS

EXCELLENCE IN RESEARCH

- Achievement of the Severo Ochoa award and of the "A" score of CERCA for the centre's excellence
- Several researchers among the highly cited worldwide
- High number of stable CREAM researchers funded by other institutions: UAB, UB, CSIC and ICREA
- CREAM's contribution with cutting-edge scientific knowledge to the greatest and most complex environmental challenges facing society in the 21st century
- Location in the UAB campus, which encourages intellectual exchange and facilitates the recruiting of new talents and the access to services
- Internationalization
- Highly improved internationalisation strategy during the last years, allowing strong and successful international collaborations with both research centres and innovation networks
- Significant increase in the coordination and participation in international (mostly EU) projects
- Researchers actively involved in international and European scientific networks (IPCC, IPBES, MedECC, ALTER-Net, GEOSS...)

KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER AND SOCIETAL IMPACT OF RESEARCH

- Consolidated technical support and knowledge transfer to local administrators
- Consolidation of CREAM as an instrument of the Catalan Government
- Centre of reference in Citizen Science
- Fundraising strategy in agreement with Terra Foundation

SUSTAINABLE GROWTH

- Grand agreement with the Catalan Government ensuring basal funding (hard money)
- Awarded with the HRS4R label
- Mention of towards excellence of the PhD programme
- Excellent support staff for researchers
- Highly efficient Communication & Outreach strategy
- Achievement of new spaces at the UAB for CREAM
- Flexible working conditions

WEAKNESSES

EXCELLENCE IN RESEARCH

- Unbalanced permanent research staff composition largely composed of male Spanish scientists
- Low rate of established international researchers
- High age of the most competitive researchers in the centre with no obvious turnover
- Low interaction between junior and senior researchers working in different research groups
- Shortage of research infrastructures and support staff
- Lack of meeting and discussion spaces for intellectual exchange

INTERNATIONALIZATION

- Lack of a successful strategy to obtain ERC grants
- Low number of researchers involved in EU- SC projects
- Lack of specific mechanisms to identify and attract the best national and international talent

KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER AND SOCIETAL IMPACT OF RESEARCH

- Reduced collaboration with private companies and potential patrons and sponsors

SUSTAINABLE GROWTH

- Little structural funding
- Important limitation of space in the centre, especially since the achievement of the Severo Ochoa award
- Heterogeneous involvement of research staff in centre's initiatives
- Guidelines on knowledge transfer and data protection, open data and licensing policies not yet well-established

OPPORTUNITIES

- Global climate emergency
- Global biodiversity loss
- Global health paradigm
- Green infrastructure paradigm
- Growing concern and socio-political awareness about the consequences of climate change
- Growing importance of international institutions related to CREAM topics, such as IPCC or IPBES
- Adoption of the UN SDGs and the 2030 Agenda by EU governments
- Mediterranean ecosystems and societies are among the most impacted by global change drivers
- Role of SOMMa (association of Severo Ochoa and María de Maeztu centres) in policy decisions with a scientific component in Spain
- Agreement with Collserola Park to share Can Balasc as a biological station

THREATS

- Highly unfavourable Catalan and Spanish financial context
- Post COVID-19 challenges
- Reduced investment in environmental research compared to other governmental needs
- Low number of competitive calls to consolidate young talented and promising researchers
- Virtually non-existent public funds to consolidate specialised administrative and technical support staff
- Limited funds for the maintenance of long-term monitoring infrastructures
- Lack of fundraising culture among companies and private individuals in Spain
- Existing biased institutional practices (often unconscious) in the evaluation of merit and suitability for leadership of female researchers

6.2. PRIORITIES 2024-2028

Considering CREAM's track record and the results obtained to date, the societal, political and economic context, and the SWOT analysis, the following strategic priorities have been established for the period 2024-2028:

1. Conduct and foster excellent scientific research relevant in a changing global context that enhances our leadership positioning at the national and international level
2. To generate societal impact from CREAM's research, contributing to current and future human well-being by ensuring environmental sustainability, by means of knowledge and technology transfer
3. To attract, retain and consolidate the talent that the center needs to fulfil its mission
4. To ensure the center's development and sustainability

In setting the strategy towards reaching these challenges, we will commit to embrace excellence across all our actions.

7. OBJECTIVES, AXES AND ACTIONS

The strategic priorities defined in the previous chapter have been developed in **16 strategic goals, 40 operational goals and 66 actions**, detailed in the following pages (actions included in the Severo Ochoa Strategic Plan are indicated with the code [SO AXX], being XX the action number in that plan).

In the area of **research**, efforts will focus on maximising CREAM's contribution to solving the major environmental challenges of the present and the future, and on promoting a culture of excellence and internal collaboration. To this end, we will be reviewing and updating when needed our scientific agenda in line with the priorities of international agendas and seeking synergies with other entities. All this, looking for the greatest possible international projection of our work and offering our team the most advanced technologies and infrastructures for the development of their research.

Of course, we want to maximise the **societal impact** of our research, first of all by introducing and fostering the impact perspective in our research strategy and practice, from planning to evaluation, and includ-

ing the development of consistent impact narratives. In this perspective, our science-to-policy work and our outreach activities shall require special attention. We will also analyse the market and social trends to find new opportunities for knowledge and technology transfer and we will develop a new KTT strategy.

In the **talent** axe, the priorities will be to fully develop the recruitment and talent management policies and systems, be able to attract the people the organisation will need to accomplish all their objectives, offer useful and comprehensive training programmes and career services, and foster the JEDI (just, equitable, diverse & inclusive) culture within CREAM.

Finally, to be a **sustainable and efficient organisation**, we must, on one hand, reduce our CO2 emissions and implement policies and procedures to be ecologically sustainable. On the other hand, we must explore our growing potential and take actions to guarantee the future increase of resources. Reviewing and improving our management model and creating the best work environment will be key assets for this purpose.

Table 7: Strategic and operational goals and actions per area

RESEARCH

ASPIRATION: STRATEGIC GOALS	HOW TO ACHIEVE IT	
	OPERATIONAL GOALS	ACTIONS
SG.1 To foster trailblazing scientific research—both basic and applied—with potential to contribute to cutting-edge solutions to global environmental and social challenges	OG.1.1 To review CREAM research areas evaluating their potential to face current and future scientific and environmental challenges	A.1. Revised CREAM’s scientific agenda
	OG.1.2 To explore the alignment of major research lines to regional, national, and international agendas (e.g., SDGs, UN 2030)	A.2. Specific addendum to CREAM’s scientific agenda
	OG.1.3. To explore agreements with the main academic trustees (UAB, UB, CSIC) to align our research agenda to their priorities.	A.3. Specific addendum to CREAM’s scientific agenda
SG.2 To cultivate and enhance a nurturing research culture for excellence	OG.2.1 To encourage CREAM’s participation and leadership at targeted EU Projects	A.4. Provide economic incentives for leadership [SO A3.2 (young researchers)]
	OG.2.2 To enhance internal collaborations among research groups	A.5. To develop an internal dynamization programme to foster collaboration among groups and researchers (including CREAM talks, Journal Clubs, Severo Ochoa Synthesis Actions, themed ‘vermut’) [SO A1.1, A1.2, A1.3]
	OG.2.3 To foster Open Science practices into CREAM’s research culture	A.6. To develop a Research Integrity Promotion Plan for implementing CREAM’s Code of Conduct A.7. To align CREAM to the current research assessment trends and research integrity practices [SO A5.1] A.8. To promote a creative and interdisciplinary dialogue between science and the arts by consolidating an artist-in-residence programme (ECOTONS) [SO A5.5]

SG.3 To position CREAM as a cutting-edge scientific institution internationally	OG.3.1 To promote the international exchange of researchers	A.9. To develop the CREAM mobility programme [SO A14.3]
	OG.3.2 To increase CREAM's presence and participation in international research and environmental initiatives and platforms	A.10. To involve CREAM researchers in intergovernmental initiatives and platforms (e.g., IPBES, IPCC, UNFCCC, CBD, WUF, etc.) [SO A14.2]
	OG.3.3 To consolidate our position as a referent scientific institution in the Mediterranean	A.11. To develop a specific strategy for the Mediterranean (MedCREAF) including science-to science, science-to-policy and science-to-business dimensions [SO A14.1]
	OG.3.4 To improve CREAM's international visibility	A.12. To develop the international communication pillar within the CREAM Communication Plan. A.13. To support leadership of CREAM researchers in international scientific and decision-making panels and workshops [SO A14.2]
	OG.3.5 To increase CREAM's visibility in the global community working on ecological modelling and forecasting under global change' and/or as a specific action.	A.14. To consolidate CREAM Ecosystems Modelling Facility [SO A2.1, A2.2, A2.3]
SG.4 To provide our staff with state-of-the art facilities to carry out research of excellence	OG.4.1 To improve CREAM's facilities	A.15. To get additional space equivalent to one third of current facilities [SO A8.1] A.16. To design and implement a plan for the improvement of lab infrastructures and general equipment [SO A8.1] A.17. To enhance synergies between research facilities, training, and education around Can Balasc [SO A8.2]
	OG.4.2 To improve CREAM's digital infrastructure and technology	A.18. To improve access to computer services and data hosting. [SO A8.3]

SOCIETAL IMPACT OF RESEARCH

ASPIRATION: STRATEGIC GOALS	HOW TO ACHIEVE IT	
	OPERATIONAL GOALS	ACTIONS
SG.5 To work towards CREAM's own research impact culture	OG.5.1 To incorporate research impact within CREAM's institutional scientific strategy and practices	A.19. To develop a revised Research Impact Strategy and the annual Impact Plans [SO A4.1] A.20. To do specific Research Impact training actions for Societal Impact for researchers, included in the Watering Talent [SO A4.1] A.21. To set up and populate an impact service platform (support and advice services and provision of resources) [SO A4.1]
	OG.5.2 To assess CREAM's research impact potential	A.22. To structure an impact assessment and monitoring system [SO A4.3] A.23. To develop impact narratives from selected impactful research (CERCA – narratives) [SO A4.3]

SG.6 To maximise the societal impact of CREAM's research	OG.6.1 To improve and promote science-policy interfaces	A.24. To create a policy impact working group
	OG.6.2 To increase CREAM's opening to society and public support of science	A.25. To increase contents and visibility of research impact in CREAM website and outreach materials (Communication Plan Pillar) [SO A4.3] A.26. To create a working group on Citizen science, education, and participatory projects [SO A5.3]
	OG.6.3 To increase the social base of CREAM	A27. To develop a social base pillar within the CREAM Communication Plan
SG.6 To maximise the societal impact of CREAM's research	OG.7.1 To develop the knowledge and technology transfer and innovation strategy	A.28. Opportunity watch: to explore the market and social trends for CREAM's business opportunities A.29. To set up a Knowledge and Technology transfer and innovation strategy [SO A7.1] A.30. To develop the IPR Management procedures
	OG.7.2 To consolidate the communication of KTT with the Generalitat	A.31. To develop a specific pillar within the CREAM Communication Plan

TALENT

ASPIRATION: STRATEGIC GOALS	HOW TO ACHIEVE IT	
	OPERATIONAL GOALS	ACTIONS
SG.8 To improve talent management and development policies	OG.8.1 To develop CREAM career plan including the improvement of career advancement opportunities (promotion and salary)	A.32. To set up a collective bargaining agreement including career plan programme for all staff members A.33. To design and implement a talent performance assessment system for all staff members [SO A5.1]
	OG.8.2 To fully implement the OTM-R policy	A.34. To implement the planned OTM-R related actions at HRS4R plan
SG.9 To recruit researchers to ensure future sustainability	OG.9.1 To forecast personnel needs according to growth objectives	A.35. To set up a CREAM Recruiting Plan including a diagnosis and an action plan (including a reflection on quantitative– replacement – and qualitative needs).
	OG.9.2 To gain international recognition as an attractive centre for developing a professional career	A.36. To develop a branding plan for talent attraction within the CREAM Communication Plan
	OG.9.3 To recruit and support researchers leading high quality research	A.37. To consolidate the support services for strategic recruitment proposals (ERC, MSCA-PF, ICREA, etc.) [SO A12.1, A12.2. A12.3] A.38. To set up talent recruitment agreements with CSIC, UAB and UB for the secondment of new researchers [SO A12.1]
	OG 9.4. To improve the PhD Programme	A.39. To improve the support to the UAB Doctorate programme in Terrestrial Ecology A.40. To help co-funding of PhD contracts

SG.10 To develop career services for researchers	OG.10.1 To develop specific training programmes	<p>A.41. To consolidate the Watering Talents Programme including specific training in research and transversal skills [SO A11.1]</p> <p>A.42. To set up specific training for research management staff [SO A9.1]</p>
	OG.10.2 To develop the career development service	<p>A.43. To consolidate the CREAM's Career Service [SO A11.1]</p> <p>A.44. To consolidate the CREAM's Mentoring programme [SO A11.2]</p>
SG.11 To create and foster an EDI (equitable, diverse & inclusive) culture	OG.11.1 To improve equality policies by introducing the EDI approach	<p>A.45. To consolidate the EDI Committee</p> <p>A.46. To implement and evaluate CREAM's EDI plan (2024-2027)</p>

SUSTAINABLE INSTITUTION

ASPIRATION: STRATEGIC GOALS	HOW TO ACHIEVE IT	
	OPERATIONAL GOALS	ACTIONS
SG12. To ensure ecological sustainability	OG.12.1 Decrease CREAM CO2 emissions.	A.47. To design the centre's Sustainability Plan, in collaboration with UAB and the Government of Catalonia, and create a WG to lead its implementation. [SO A10.2]
SG.13 To assess the growing potential of CREAM	OG.13.1 To undertake a process of reflection on CREAM beyond 2025	A.48. To do a reflection document on CREAM beyond 2025 on CREAM size, structure, and organisation (collecting the outcome of internal discussion meetings, debates of the board of trustees, and recommendations of SAB) [SO A10.1]
SG.14 To ensure economic sustainability	OG.14.1 To undertake a process of reflection on the sustainability of the centre with the Board of Trustees.	A.49. To revise the agreements with trustees (including agreements with CSIC and UAB at action)
	OG.14.2 To increase structural funds	A.50. To revise the agreements with the Government of Catalonia
	OG.14.3 To diversify income sources	A.51. To deploy a Philanthropy Plan [SO A7.4]
		A.52. To develop Knowledge & technology-based service [SO A7.2]
	A.53. To explore Public Procurement opportunities (exploring opportunities, networking, tenders, etc) [SO A18.3]	
	OG.14.4 To design a policy of prioritisation of projects and funding opportunities	A.54. To implement a policy on prioritisation of projects and funding opportunities: publication of policy and awareness raising/training actions, funding guide

<p>SG.15 To improve the management model and make it as efficient as possible</p>	<p>OG.15.1 To enhance management efficiency and transparency</p>	<p>A.55. To set up a CRIS, a general management Information System linking project research management to outputs and impacts</p> <p>A.56.To develop and implement the centre’s Data Management Strategy</p> <p>A.57. To improve administrative protocols for reducing bureaucracy</p> <p>A.58. To develop a toolkit for teams’ assessment performance</p>
	<p>OG. 15.2. To improve the strategy and management of research projects in all phases.</p>	<p>A.59. To improve the coordination of pre- and post-award offices</p> <p>A.60.To implement FUNDANET, a specific software for project management</p>
<p>SG.16 To improve CREAM’s work environment</p>	<p>OG.16.1 To diagnose CREAM’s work environment</p>	<p>A.61. To do a satisfaction survey on CREAM’s environment and services</p> <p>A.62. To regularly do an offboarding survey</p> <p>A.63. To do a conflict management protocol</p>
	<p>OG.16.2 To implant a hybrid working model</p>	<p>A.64.To define and implement a teleworking policy</p>
	<p>OG.16.3 To promote an international working culture</p>	<p>A.65. To promote English as a CREAM working language</p>
	<p>OG.16.4 To promote internal communication</p>	<p>A.66. To develop an Internal Communication Pillar within the CREAM Communication Plan.</p>

ACTIONS CALENDAR

Table 8: Calendar of actions per area and semester (S). Those included in the Severo Ochoa strategic plan are indicated as [SO AXX], being XX the action number in that plan.

SG	ACTIONS	2024 S2	2025 S1	2025 S2	2026 S1	2026 S2	2027 S1	2027 S2	2028 S1
RESEARCH									
1	A.1. Revised CREAM's scientific agenda								
1	A.2. Specific addendum to CREAM's scientific agenda								
1	A.3. Specific addendum to CREAM's scientific agenda								
2	A.4. Provide economic incentives for leadership [SO A3.2 (young researchers)]								
2	A.5. To develop an internal dynamization programme to foster collaboration among groups and researchers (including CREAM talks, Severo Ochoa Synthesis Actions, themed 'vermut's') [SO A1.1, A1.2, A1.3]								
2	A.6. To develop a Research Integrity Promotion Plan for implementing CREAM's Code of Conduct								
2	A.7. To align CREAM to the current research assessment trends and research integrity practices [SO A5.1]								
2	A.8. To promote a creative and interdisciplinary dialogue between science and the arts by consolidating an artist-in-residence programme (ECO-TONS) [SO A55]								
3	A.9. To develop the CREAM mobility programme [SO A14.3]								
3	A.10. To involve CREAM researchers in intergovernmental initiatives and platforms (e.g., IPBES, IPCC, UNFCCC, CBD, WUF, etc.) [SO A14.2]								
3	A.11. To develop a specific strategy for the Mediterranean (MedCREAF) including science-for-science, science-for-policy and science-for-business dimensions [SO A14.1]								
3	A.12. To develop the international communication pillar within the CREAM Communication Plan.								
3	A.13. To support leadership of CREAM researchers in international scientific and decision-making panels and workshops [SO A14.2]								
3	A.14. To consolidate CREAM Ecosystems Modelling Facility [SO A2.1, A2.2, A2.3]								
4	A.15. To get additional space equivalent to one third of current facilities [SO A8.1]								
4	A.16. To design and implement a plan for the improvement of lab infrastructures and general equipment [SO A8.1]								
4	A.17. To enhance synergies between research facilities, training, and education around Can Balasc [SO A8.2]								
4	A.18. To improve access to computer services and data hosting. [SO A8.3]								

SG	ACTIONS	2024 S2	2025 S1	2025 S2	2026 S1	2026 S2	2027 S1	2027 S2	2028 S1
SOCIETAL IMPACT OF RESEARCH									
5	A.19. To develop a revised Research Impact Strategy and the annual Impact Plans [SO A4.1]								
5	A.20. To do specific Research Impact training actions for researchers, included in the Watering Talent [SO A4.1]								
5	A.21. To set up and populate an impact service platform (support and advice services and provision of resources) [SO A4.1]								
5	A.22. To structure an Impact assessment and monitoring system [SO A4.3]								
5	A.23. To develop impact narratives from selected impactful research (CERCA – narratives) [SO A4.3]								
6	A.24. To create a policy impact working group								
6	A.25. To increase contents and visibility of research impact in CREAM website and outreach materials (Communication Plan Pillar). [SO A4.3]								
6	A.26. To create a working group on Citizen science, education, and participatory projects [SO A5.3]								
6	A.27. To develop a social base pillar within the CREAM Communication Plan								
7	A.28. Opportunity watch: to explore the market and social trends for CREAM's bussiness opportunities								
7	A.29. To set up a Knowledge and Technology transfer and innovation strategy [SO A7.1]								
7	A.30. To develop the IPR Management procedures								
7	A.31. To develop a specific pillar within the CREAM Communication Plan								
TALENT									
8	A.32. To set up a collective bargaining agreement including career plan programme for all staff members								
8	A.33. To design and implement a talent performance assessment system for all staff members [SO A5.1]								
8	A.34. To implement the planned OTM-R actions at HRS4R plan								
9	A.35. To set up a CREAM Recruiting Plan including a diagnosis and an action plan (including a reflection on quantitative – replacement – and qualitative needs)								
9	A.36. To develop a branding plan for talent attraction within the CREAM Communication Plan								
9	A.37. To consolidate the support services for strategic recruitment proposals (ERC, MSCA-PF, ICREA, etc.) [SO A12.1, A12.2. A12.3]								
9	A.38. To set up talent recruitment agreements with CSIC, UAB and UB for the secondment of new researchers [SO A12.1]								
9	A.39. To improve the support to the UAB Doctorate programme in Terrestrial Ecology								
9	A.40. To help co-funding of PhD contracts								

SG	ACTIONS	2024 S2	2025 S1	2025 S2	2026 S1	2026 S2	2027 S1	2027 S2	2028 S1
10	A.41. To consolidate the Watering Talents Programme including specific training in research and transversal skills [SO A11.1]								
10	A.42. To set up specific training for research management staff [SO A9.1]								
10	A.43. To consolidate CREAM's Career Service [SO A11.1]								
10	A.44. To consolidate CREAM's Mentoring programme [SO A11.2]								
11	A.45. To consolidate the EDI Committee								
11	A.46. To implement and evaluate CREAM's EDI Plan (2024-2027)								
SUSTAINABLE INSTITUTION									
12	A.47. To design the centre's Sustainability Plan, in collaboration with UAB and the Government of Catalonia, and create a WG to lead its implementation. [SO A10.2]								
13	A.48. To do a reflection document on CREAM beyond 2025 on CREAM size, structure, and organisation (collecting the outcome of internal discussion meetings, debates of the board of trustees, and recommendations of SAB) [SO A10.1]								
14	A.49. To revise the agreements with trustees (including agreements with CSIC and UAB at action)								
14	A.50. To revise the agreements with the Government of Catalonia								
14	A.51. To deploy a Philanthropy Plan [SO A7.4]								
14	A.52. To develop Knowledge & technology-based service [SO A7.2]								
14	A.53. To explore Public Procurement opportunities (exploring opportunities, networking, tenders, etc) [SO A18.3]								
14	A.54. To implement a policy on prioritisation of projects and funding opportunities: publication of policy and awareness raising/training actions, funding guide								
15	A.55. To set up a CRIS, management Information System linking project/research management to finance, outputs, and impacts								
15	A.56. To develop and implementation of the centre's Data Management Strategy								
15	A.57. To improve administrative protocols for reducing bureaucracy								
15	A.58. To develop a toolkit for teams' assessment performance								
15	A.59. To improve the coordination of pre- and post-award offices								
15	A.60. To implement FUNDANET, a specific software for project management								
16	A.61. To do a satisfaction survey on CREAM's environment and services								
16	A.62. To regularly do an offboarding survey								

SG	ACTIONS	2024 S2	2025 S1	2025 S2	2026 S1	2026 S2	2027 S1	2027 S2	2028 S1
16	A.63. To do a conflict management protocol								
16	A.64. To define and implement a teleworking policy								
16	A.65. To promote English as CREAM working language								
16	A.66. To develop an Internal Communication Pillar within the CREAM Communication Plan.								

8. MONITORING AND EVALUATION

Table 9: Key Performance Indicators (KPI) and values of reference and to be achieved per strategic goal (SG)

SG	KPI	RESPONSIBLE OF EXECUTION	REFERENCE VALUE	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2024-2028
1	KPI1. A revised scientific agenda of CREAM	Director-CRD	-			Y			Y
2	KPI2. Proportion of CREAM budget coming from EU (International) funding = (EU funding €) / (Total CREAM budget €)	Post-award officer	30	31	32	33	34	35	32.5
2	KPI3. CoARA action plan developed	CoARA working group	-	Y				Y (Reviewed)	
3	KPI4. MedCREAF strategy developed	Institutional relations officer	-	Y	(Published)				
3	KPI5. Science diplomacy and science 4 policy strategies and structures	Institutional relations officer	-		Y				
3	KPI6. A consolidated Ecosystems Modelling Facility (EMF)	Director-CRD	-				Y		
4	KPI7. Additional space of at least 1000 m2 achieved	Director-Manager				Y			
4	KPI8. Consolidated lab facilities of CREAM	Manager-CRD	-			Y			
4	KPI9. Consolidated digital infrastructure of CREAM	Manager-CRD	-		Y				
5	KPI10. Impact assessment and monitoring system structured	Research Impact Officer	-					Y	
6	KPI11. Impact service platform developed.	Research Impact Officer	-				Y		
6	KPI12. Social engagement (impressions in SSNN)	Communication officer	4.0M	4.0M	4.5M	5.0M	5.5M	5.5M	4.25M (mean)
6	KPI13. International engagement (% of foreigner followers)	Communication officer	30%	36%	40%	42%	45%	45%	40.7%
7	KPI14. KTT Strategy developed.	Transfer Officer	-	Y					
8	KPI15. New collective bargaining agreement implemented including a career promotion plan for all staff	Manager- Human resources officer	Y						

SG	KPI	RESPONSIBLE OF EXECUTION	REFERENCE VALUE	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2024-2028
9	KPI16. Annual number of R1 (predoctoral) researchers	PhD Program Coordinator – Academic Talent and EDI officer	41	42	43	44	45	46	44 (mean)
9	KPI17. Total number of successful ERC grants, MSCA-PF and Ramón y Cajal grants for R2, R3 and R4 researchers.	Academic Talent and EDI officer	ERC StG: 1 MSCA-PF: 5 RyC: 2						ERC StG/ CoG/AdG: 1 MSCA-PF: 5 RyC: 2
9	KPI18. Total number of new permanent seconded researchers (ICREA, UAB, UB, CSIC).	Academic Talent and EDI officer	6	2	2	2	3	3	12 (total)
10	KPI19. Number of courses with >10 participants in the Watering Talents training programme	Academic Talent and EDI officer	16	14	15	16	17	18	16
11	KPI20. Diversity of research staff during 2024-2028 = (percentage of recruited researchers that are women).	Academic Talent and EDI officer	43% (mean 2020-2023)						> 40% (mean)
11	KPI21. % of PI (or CREAM-PI) researchers in national or international projects that are women	Academic Talent and EDI officer	28	35	37	40	43	45	40
12	KPI22. Approval of the sustainability plan	Direction-Manager			Y				
13	KPI23. Reflection document finished	Direction-Manager			Y				
14	KPI24. Distance of structure funds to 33% of total (in % of total)	Manager	9 (2023)	8	7	6	5	3	6
14	KPI25. Amount of irregular funds (Philanthropy & TechTransfer)	Manager	25 000€	30 000€	50 000€	75 000€	90 000€	90 000€	67 000€
15	KPI26. Level of implementation of the process map (% of processes implemented)	Manager	0	25	50	67	85	100	65
15	KPI27. Data Management Strategy developed	Manager			Y				
16	KPI28. Employee Engagement/Satisfaction (Survey Scores, max 10):	Human resources officer	-	5		6		7	6

9. FINANCIAL PROSPECTS

Estimated costs of the planned actions are summarised in table 10. They are based on the Severo Ochoa Award funds, the contributions of the programme contract with the Catalan Government and internal resources.

Table 10: Costs and funding sources per action

SG	ACTION	INTERNAL RESOURCES	GRAND AGREEMENT	SEVERO OCHOA	TOTAL
1	A.1. Revised CREAM's scientific agenda	5000			5000
1	A.2. Specific addendum to CREAM's scientific agenda				0
1	A.3. Specific addendum to CREAM's scientific agenda				0
2	A.4. Provide economic incentives for leadership [SO A3.2 (young researchers)]			60000	60000
2	A.5. To develop an internal dynamization programme to foster collaboration among groups and researchers (including CREAM talks, Severo Ochoa Synthesis Actions, themed 'vermut's') [SO A1.1, A1.2, A1.3]			110000	110000
2	A.6. To develop a Research Integrity Promotion Plan for implementing CREAM's Code of Conduct	5000			5000
2	A.7. To align CREAM to the current research assessment trends and research integrity practices [SO A5.1]			6000	6000
2	A.8. To promote a creative and interdisciplinary dialogue between science and the arts by consolidating an artist-in-residence programme (ECOTONS) [SO A5.5]			40000	40000
3	A.9. To develop the CREAM mobility programme [SO A14.3]			85000	85000
3	A.10. To involve CREAM researchers in intergovernmental initiatives and platforms (e.g., IPBES, IPCC, UNFCCC, CBD, WUF, etc.) [SO A14.2]		10000	10000	20000
3	A.11. To develop a specific strategy for the Mediterranean (Med-CREAM) including science-for-science, science-for-policy and science-for-business dimensions [SO A14.1]			150000	150000
3	A.12. To develop the international communication pillar within the CREAM Communication Plan.	5000			5000
3	A.13. To support leadership of CREAM researchers in international scientific and decision-making panels and workshops [SO A14.2]		10000	15000	25000
3	A.14. To consolidate CREAM Ecosystems Modelling Facility [SO A2.1, A2.2, A2.3]			368000	368000
4	A.15. To get additional space equivalent to one third of current facilities [SO A8.1]		1000000		1000000
4	A.16. To design and implement a plan for the improvement of lab infrastructures and general equipment [SO A8.1]			260000	280000
4	A.17. To enhance synergies between research facilities, training, and education around Can Balasc [SO A8.2]			10000	10000
4	A.18. To improve access to computer services and data hosting. [SO A8.3]			150000	150000
5	A.19. To develop a revised Research Impact Strategy and the annual Impact Plans [SO A4.1]	5000			5000
5	A.20. To do specific Research Impact training actions for researchers, included in the Watering Talent [SO A4.1]			5000	5000

SG	ACTION	INTERNAL RESOURCES	GRAND AGREEMENT	SEVERO OCHOA	TOTAL
5	A.21. To set up and populate an impact service platform (support and advice services and provision of resources) [SO A4.1]			15000	15000
5	A.22. To structure an Impact assessment and monitoring system [SO A4.3]			15000	15000
5	A.23. To develop impact narratives from selected impactful research (CERCA – narratives) [SO A4.3]	10000		5000	15000
6	A.24. To create a policy impact working group				0
6	A.25. To increase contents and visibility of research impact in CREAM website and outreach materials (Communication Plan Pillar). [SO A4.3]	5000			5000
6	A.26. To create a working group on Citizen science, education, and participatory projects [SO A5.3]				0
6	A.27. To develop a social base pillar within the CREAM Communication Plan	5000			5000
7	A.28. Opportunity watch: to explore the market and social trends for CREAM's business opportunities	5000			5000
7	A.29. To set up a Knowledge and Technology transfer and innovation strategy [SO A7.1]			140000	140000
7	A.30. To develop the IPR Management procedures	5000			5000
7	A.31. To develop a specific pillar within the CREAM Communication Plan	5000			5000
8	A.32. To set up a collective bargaining agreement including career plan programme for all staff members	5000			5000
8	A.33. To design and implement a talent performance assessment system for all staff members [SO A5.1]			6000	6000
8	A.34. To implement the planned OTM-R actions at HRS4R plan	5000			5000
9	A.35. To set up a CREAM Recruiting Plan including a diagnosis and an action plan (including a reflection on quantitative – replacement – and qualitative needs)	5000			5000
9	A.36. To develop a branding plan for talent attraction within the CREAM Communication Plan	10000			10000
9	A.37. To consolidate the support services for strategic recruitment proposals (ERC, MSCA-PF, ICREA, etc.) [SO A12.1, A12.2, A12.3]			820000	820000
9	A.38. To set up talent recruitment agreements with CSIC, UAB and UB for the secondment of new researchers [SO A12.1]				0
9	A.39. To improve the support to the UAB Doctorate programme in Terrestrial Ecology	5000			5000
9	A.40. To help co-funding of PhD contracts		100000		100000
10	A.41. To consolidate the Watering Talents Programme including specific training in research and transversal skills [SO A11.1]			5000	5000
10	A.42. To set up specific training for research management staff [SO A9.1]			64000	64000
10	A.43. To consolidate CREAM's Career Service [SO A11.1]			45000	45000
10	A.44. To consolidate CREAM's Mentoring programme [SO A11.2]			5000	5000
11	A.45. To consolidate the EDI Committee				0
11	A.46. To implement and evaluate CREAM's EDI Plan (2024-2027)	5000			5000
12	A.47. To design the centre's Sustainability Plan, in collaboration with UAB and the Government of Catalonia, and create a WG to lead its implementation. [SO A10.2]			9000	9000

SG	ACTION	INTERNAL RESOURCES	GRAND AGREEMENT	SEVERO OCHOA	TOTAL
13	A.48. To do a reflection document on CREAM beyond 2025 on CREAM size, structure, and organisation (collecting the outcome of internal discussion meetings, debates of the board of trustees, and recommendations of SAB) [SO A10.1]	5000			5000
14	A.49. To revise the agreements with trustees (including agreements with CSIC and UAB at action)				0
14	A.50. To revise the agreements with the Government of Catalonia				0
14	A.51. To deploy a Philanthropy Plan [SO A7.4]			40000	40000
14	A.52. To develop Knowledge & technology-based service [SO A7.2]			63000	63000
14	A.53. To explore Public Procurement opportunities (exploring opportunities, networking, tenders, etc) [SO A18.3]			5000	5000
14	A.54. To implement a policy on prioritisation of projects and funding opportunities: publication of policy and awareness raising/training actions, funding guide				0
15	A.55. To set up a CRIS, management Information System linking project/research management to finance, outputs, and impacts		30000		30000
15	A.56. To develop and implementation of the centre's Data Management Strategy	5000			5000
15	A.57. To improve administrative protocols for reducing bureaucracy	5000			5000
15	A.58. To develop a toolkit for teams' assessment performance	5000			5000
15	A.59. To improve the coordination of pre- and post-award offices				0
15	A.60. To implement FUNDANET, a specific software for project management		140000		140000
16	A.61. To do a satisfaction survey on CREAM's environment and services	5000			5000
16	A.62. To regularly do an offboarding survey				0
16	A.63. To do a conflict management protocol	5000			5000
16	A.64. To define and implement a teleworking policy	50000			50000
16	A.65. To promote English as CREAM working language	5000			5000
16	A.66. To develop an Internal Communication Pillar within the CREAM Communication Plan.	5000			5000
		180000	1290000	2506000	3976000